

Threat Discrimination Between Attacks and Faults for a Class of Nonlinear Systems

Kangkang Zhang, Andreas Kasis, Thomas Parisini, *Fellow, IEEE*, and Marios M. Polycarpou, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—This paper addresses the problem of detecting and discriminating threats in cyber-physical systems, where the threats may be physical faults and cyber-attacks. We propose a sensor switching watermark scheme, composed of a watermark generator and a remover, both switching between a set of two larger (outer) and two smaller (inner) values. We show that threat detection and discrimination are achieved by properly setting these values and the switching times. In particular, the proposed methodology can handle a class of physical faults and a broad range of man-in-the-middle cyber attacks such as replay attacks and integrity attacks. A key feature of our methodology is the unpredictable switching time instants that entail a combination of random elements and private time seeds. In addition, we provide suitable design requirements for the time seeds and demonstrate how these are satisfied by a chaotic Lorenz system. Finally, we illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology by numerical simulations.

Index Terms—Cyber-physical threats, sensor switching watermark, threat detection and discrimination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber-physical systems (CPS) characterize various safety-critical infrastructure systems. Water and electric power distribution systems are two typical examples that highly depend on various networked information technologies such as Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems. In water systems, many chemical and biological parameters (such as chlorine concentration, colour conductivity, pH and temperature) and hydraulic variables (such as flows and pressures), are remotely monitored by online sensors and sent through SCADA systems [2] to control stations. Power flows are remotely measured and transmitted over SCADA systems in power transmission networks [3]. Due to the complex integration of information technologies and physical processes, cyber-physical systems are vulnerable to, apart from traditional physical faults, new emerging threats such as cyber

attacks [4]. Cyber-attack events, such as Stuxnet, Blackenergy, Industroyer, and Triton, have been witnessed in the past two decades [5]. This work considers physical faults and cyber attacks and aims to address some key open research challenges of detection and discrimination.

Research efforts on the diagnosis of general threats (including cyber-attacks and physical faults) have been conducted more recently. Threat detection, as the typical fault diagnosis, aims to detect the occurrence of threats. The purpose of threat discrimination is to determine the type of occurring threats (cyber attacks or physical faults). It is worth pointing out that typical fault isolation approaches that locate faulty components, are in general not suitable for threat discrimination.

Threat detection and discrimination approaches are broadly classified into two main categories: i) passive approaches (see, *e.g.*, [6]–[9]), and ii) active approaches (see, for instance, [10], [11]). Passive approaches are often not effective for diagnosing perfectly stealthy attacks such as the ones in [12]–[15]. Threat discrimination has only been investigated recently (see, *e.g.*, [6], [7], [16]). The authors' previous works [6], [7] explore it by considering simple constant faults using adaptive identifying observers. Active approaches are more effective but may simultaneously degrade control performance due to the injected extra input. To the best of the authors' knowledge, active threat discrimination has not yet been addressed in the literature. As a typical active approach, watermark approaches have been studied in the recent literature [17]–[19]. A typical watermark methodology leverages an actuator watermark added to the control input as an authentication. The discrepancy of the received authentication is utilized to indicate the occurrence of an attack [11]. However, actuator watermarks inevitably cause control performance degradation since an input disturbance is injected into the physical process.

Cryptographic techniques, such as the homomorphic encryption [20], the Paillier cryptosystem [21], and the encryption-decryption method [22], which aim to preserve privacy, have been extended to the area of attack detection. Sensor watermark approaches, consisting of a watermark generator (encryption) and a watermark remover (decryption), have been leveraged to meet the attack detection requirement and avoid degrading the control performance when no cyber attack occurs. A sensor multiplicative watermark approach is proposed in [23], where two mutual reciprocal switching dynamical systems, respectively working as the generator and remover, multiply the encrypted sensor measurements. This approach may significantly affect the stability of the closed-loop system when the switches of the mutual reciprocal dynamical systems are asynchronized in the presence of a cyber attack. A sensor additive watermark approach is used in [24], where Gaussian white noise is leveraged as the

This work has been supported by: the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101027980 (CSP-CPS-A-ICA), No. 891101 (SmarTher Grid) and No. 739551 (KIOS CoE-TEAMING). An earlier version of this paper was presented at the 11th SAFEPROCESS Conference and appeared in [1].

Kangkang Zhang is with the College of Automation Engineering, Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Nanjing 211106, China, zhang.kangkang@nuaa.edu.cn

T. Parisini is with the Dept. of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Imperial College London, London, SW7 2AZ, UK and also with the Department of Engineering and Architecture, University of Trieste, Italy, t.parisini@gmail.com

A. Kasis and M. Polycarpou are with the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, and the Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, 1678, Cyprus, kasis.andreas@ucy.ac.cy; mpolycar@ucy.ac.cy

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of sensor additive switching watermark scheme.

watermark to the encrypted sensor measurements. Although not compromising system stability, this approach degrades the control performance since the used stochastic watermark cannot be deterministically cancelled out. This approach is also used in [25] and [26] to detect replay attacks by generating the watermark using a standard pseudo-random number generator with a one-bit key. However, the simple one-bit key may be easily learned and countered by the attacker. In the context of threat discrimination, pseudo-random watermark schemes, unless suitably designed, do not enable a distinction between faults and cyber attacks. Conclusively, the watermark design is key to achieve threat detection and discrimination, and also confidentiality.

Contribution: This paper proposes a switching watermark approach with particularly designed switching protocols and watermarks to achieve detection and discrimination between faults and cyber attacks. The proposed sensor additive switching watermark scheme is depicted in Fig. 1 where the sensor measurement is encrypted by adding the switching watermark produced by the generator before transmitted, and is decrypted by subtracting the switching watermark produced by the remover before received by the controller and anomaly detector. The switch-triggering protocol design enables the switch synchronization to be sensitive to cyber attacks but not faults, thereby enabling threat discrimination. Further details are provided below.

The proposed watermark scheme includes outer and inner switches, switching between a set of two larger (outer) and two smaller (inner) values. This is combined with an observer-based anomaly detector and a *bi-layer decision strategy* to form a framework that enables threat detection and discrimination for a class of nonlinear systems. The outer-switch triggering protocols and the values of the watermark are jointly designed such that switch asynchronization occurs only when a cyber attack is present. The designed protocols, including a random time-dependent and a system output-dependent triggering condition, produce randomized outer switching time instants that are unpredictable to the attacker.

For the inner watermark trajectory, the intersection points of the trajectory of a chaotic Lorenz system driven by a private initial condition and a given plane are proposed as its inner switch times, where the initial condition plays the role of the one bit secret key. The Lorenz system's expansive property ensures that each intersection point is highly sensitive to the secret key, thereby empowering the inner switch times with confidentiality. A sequence of keys is designed such that the switches of all the inner switch trajectories are scheduled, ensuring that the root-mean-square (RMS) of the difference between any two inner switch trajectories is sufficiently large. Then, the detection and discrimination between physical faults

and a broad range of MITM cyber attacks such as replay and stealthy integrity attacks, are rigorously guaranteed by designing the sequence of the secret keys.

In short, the main contributions are summarized as follows:

- (i) A novel methodology is proposed, integrating a suitably designed sensor switching watermark and a *bi-layer decision strategy* based on an anomaly detector, to achieve threat detection and discrimination;
- (ii) By suitably designing a private key sequence, through a Lorenz system, the switch times of the proposed methodology become confidential.

The sensor additive watermark approach developed in this paper is constrained within a set of certain values, which is more practical compared to the monotonically increasing watermark used in the authors' previous work [1]. In contrast to the multiplicative watermark approach [23], which may compromise closed-loop stability in the presence of attacks, the proposed additive watermark, which can be considered as a bounded disturbance, preserves the stability of most practical closed-loop systems. Compared with the typical actuator watermark approaches such as [11], [19] that degrade control performance, this approach maintains the control performance in the absence of an attack. Instead of using Gaussian white process [24] and pseudo-random numbers [25], [26] as the watermark, this approach leverages the particularly designed switching watermarks, allowing to deterministically guarantee detection and discrimination for a broad range of cyber attacks.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we present the problem formulation. In Sections III and IV, the sensor watermark methodology is presented. The detectability and discrimination capabilities are analyzed in Section V, and the feasible Lorenz time seeds are given in Section VI. Simulation results and concluding remarks are respectively provided in Section VII and VIII.

Notations and Preliminaries. Let \mathbb{C} , \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{Q} , and \mathbb{N} represent complex, real, rational, and natural numbers, respectively, and \mathbb{R}^n represent the n -dimensional real space. For any $N \in \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbb{R}_{\geq N}$, $\mathbb{Q}_{\geq N}$, and $\mathbb{N}_{\geq N}$ represent real, rational and natural numbers not less than N , respectively, $\mathbb{N}_{[N_1, N_2]}$ represents the natural number set from N_1 to N_2 for some natural numbers $N_1 \leq N_2$. For $t_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, we denote $t_0^+ = \lim_{t \downarrow t_0} t$. The notation $|\cdot|$ represents the absolute value for scalars and the Euclidean 2-norm for vectors and matrices. For $x \in \mathbb{R}$, the Heaviside function satisfies $H(x) = 1$ for $x \geq 0$, and 0 for $x < 0$. For a vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\text{sgn}(x) = \text{diag}(\text{sign}(x_1), \dots, \text{sign}(x_n))$. For a function $f(t)$ and $t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, $f(t) \equiv 0$ means $f(t) = 0$ identically for all $t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, $f(t) \not\equiv 0$ means $f(t) \neq 0$ for some $t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. For a matrix A , we use $\underline{\sigma}(A)$ and $\bar{\sigma}(A)$ to represent the minimum and maximum singular values respectively.

Signals [27]: The finite-horizon Lebesgue 2-space $\mathcal{L}_2[0, T]$ is $\mathcal{L}_2[0, T] \triangleq \{x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n : \|x\|_{[0, T]} \triangleq \int_0^T x^T(t)x(t)dt < \infty\}$. The infinite horizon Lebesgue 2-space $\mathcal{L}_2[0, \infty)$ is $\mathcal{L}_2[0, \infty) \triangleq \{x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n : \|x\|_{[0, \infty)} \triangleq \int_0^\infty x^T(t)x(t)dt < \infty\}$. The RMS of signal x in the time interval $(t - \kappa, t]$ with the length $\kappa > 0$ is denoted by $\|x(t)\|_{R, \kappa} \triangleq \sqrt{\frac{1}{\kappa} \int_{t-\kappa}^t x^T(\tau)x(\tau)dt}$. The average energy for the time interval $[0, t]$ is $\|x(t)\| \triangleq$

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{t} \int_0^t x^T(\tau)x(\tau)d\tau}.$$

Systems: Consider a stable linear time-invariant system with the transfer matrix $G(s) \in \mathcal{RH}_\infty$ for $s \in \mathbb{C}$. We can define a corresponding convolution operator $M_G : \mathcal{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_2$, where $M_G u \triangleq \int_0^t g(t-\tau)u(\tau)d\tau$, where $g(t)$ is the impulse response of the system $G(s)$. Then, for the transfer matrix $G(s) \in \mathcal{RH}_\infty$, the \mathcal{H}_∞ norm is given by $\|G\|_\infty = \sup_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}} \bar{\sigma}(G(j\omega))$. Moreover, its \mathcal{H}_- index in the frequency domain and the time domain are defined below.

Definition 1. [28] For the transfer matrix $G(s) \in \mathcal{RH}_\infty$, the \mathcal{H}_- index is defined as

$$\|G\|_- = \inf_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}} \underline{\sigma}(G(j\omega)). \quad (1)$$

For the operator M_G , the induced $\|M_G\|_-$ index in the finite-time horizon $[0, T]$ is defined as follows:

$$\|M_G\|_-^{[0, T]} = \inf_{u \neq 0, u \in \mathcal{L}_2[0, T]} \frac{\|M_G u\|_{[0, T]}}{\|u\|_{[0, T]}}, \quad (2)$$

and in the infinite-time horizon,

$$\|M_G\|_-^{[0, \infty)} = \inf_{u \neq 0, u \in \mathcal{L}_2[0, \infty)} \frac{\|M_G u\|_{[0, \infty)}}{\|u\|_{[0, \infty)}}. \quad (3)$$

Lemma 1. For any $u \in \mathcal{L}_2[0, T]$ with $T > 0$ and any transfer matrix $G(s) \in \mathcal{RH}_\infty$ with corresponding convolution operator M_G , we have

$$\|M_G u\| \geq \|G\|_- \|u\| \geq \frac{\sqrt{\kappa}}{\sqrt{t}} \|G\|_- \|u\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}, \quad (4)$$

where $\kappa > 0$ and $0 < t < T$ are the evaluation time lengths of the RMS $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}$ and average energy $\|\cdot\|$ operators, respectively.

Proof. Let $\psi(t) \triangleq \inf_{u \neq 0, u \in \mathcal{L}_2[0, \infty)} \frac{\|M_G u\|_{[0, t]}}{\|u\|_{[0, t]}}$ for $t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \cup \{+\infty\}$. Then, it can be straightforwardly inferred that $\psi(t)$ is a non-increasing monotone function since for any $t_2 \geq t_1 > 0$, $\psi(t_2) \leq \psi(t_1)$. In addition, since $\|G\|_-$ exists and $\|M_G\|_-^{[0, \infty)} = \|G\|_-$ (inferred from [29]), we have $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \psi(t) = \|G\|_-$. Hence, we can observe that $\psi(t) \geq \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \psi(t) = \|G\|_-$, and thus,

$$\|M_G u\| = \|M_G u\|_{[0, t]} \geq \|M_G\|_-^{[0, t]} \|u\| \geq \|G\|_- \|u\|. \quad (5)$$

Moreover, the average energy in $[0, t]$ and the RMS in $[t-\kappa, t]$ satisfy $\|u\| \geq \frac{\sqrt{\kappa}}{\sqrt{t}} \|u\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}$. Hence, the result follows. \square

Lemma 1 shows that for a linear time-invariant system, the average energy of its output during a finite time interval can be arbitrarily enlarged by increasing the RMS of its input at some time of this time interval if the \mathcal{H}_- index defined in [28] from the input to the output is nonzero. This finding is used to design the inner watermark trajectory such that the average energy of the detection residual is allowed to exceed any required threshold in the presence of the attack. The detailed design is given below.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Networked Control System

In this paper, two types of threats are considered: i) MITM cyber attacks, and ii) general physical faults. In the absence of the watermark generator and remover in Fig. 1, the closed-loop CPS is described by

$$\dot{x} = Ax + \rho(x(t), t) + B_f f(t) + B_a a_u(t) + B_d d(t), \quad (6a)$$

$$y_p = Cx + D_f f(t) + D_d d(t), \quad (6b)$$

$$y_q = y_p + a_y(t), \quad (6c)$$

where $x \in \mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (\mathcal{X} is a closed compact set) represents the state of the closed-loop system including the plant and controller states, $y_p, y_q \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ respectively denote the actual sensor measurement and the measurement received by the controller and the detector from the sensor communication network, and $f \in \mathbb{R}^{n_f}$ and $d \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$ represent the physical fault and lumped disturbance respectively. Moreover, $a_u \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{a_u}}$ and $a_y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{a_y}}$ represent the actuator and sensor cyber attacks respectively. The matrices $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_f \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_f}$, $B_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_d}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n}$, $D_f \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_f}$, and $D_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_d}$ are assumed to be known by the defender. Various systems can be described by (6). Some examples are the pendulum [30], the single-link flexible joint robot [31] and the longitudinal navigation model of the air-breathing hypersonic vehicle [15]. In addition, the following assumptions are made for (6).

Assumption 1. The pair (A, C) is observable. \blacktriangle

Assumption 2. The nonlinear function $\rho : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ is known by the defender, and is piecewise continuous in t for $t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and locally Lipschitz in x for $x \in \mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, i.e.,

$$|\rho(x, t) - \rho(\hat{x}, t)| \leq \gamma |x - \hat{x}|, \quad \forall x, \hat{x} \in \mathcal{X}, t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma > 0$ is the Lipschitz constant. \blacktriangle

Remark 1. Assumptions 1 and 2 are standard technical assumptions in the fault diagnosis literature, e.g., [8], [32]. Assumption 1 requires the linear part of (6) to be observable, and the nonlinearity ρ is required to be Lipschitz continuous in Assumption 2. These are necessary conditions for the nonlinear observer design [33], [34]. Note that various nonlinearities satisfy Assumption 2 at least locally. For example, the sinusoidal function, frequently used for describing robotic dynamics, is globally Lipschitz [31], [33]. ∇

The following assumptions bound the disturbance and fault.

Assumption 3. There exists a constant $\delta_d > 0$ such that

$$|d(t)| \leq \delta_d, \quad \forall t \geq 0, \quad (8)$$

where δ_d is known by the defender. \blacktriangle

Assumption 4. The considered fault function $f(t)$ is piecewise continuous and bounded, i.e., there exists a constant (unknown to the defender) value $\delta_f > 0$ such that

$$|f(t)| \leq \delta_f, \quad \forall t \geq 0. \quad (9)$$

Moreover, the defender knows an upper bound $\bar{\delta}_f$ of δ_f , i.e., $\delta_f \leq \bar{\delta}_f$. \blacktriangle

Based on Assumptions 3 and 4, there exists a constant $\Upsilon > 0$ such that in the nominal and fault scenarios,

$$y_p \in \mathcal{Y} \triangleq \{y_p \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y} \mid |y_p| \leq \Upsilon\}. \quad (10)$$

Remark 2. Assumption 3 characterizes the bounded disturbances and noise, allowing the distinction between the effects of the disturbance and the threat. Precise knowledge of δ_d is not required but only that of an upper bound to it. The latter can be obtained by using disturbance estimation techniques based on experimental data [35]. Assumption 4 is used for threat discrimination purposes, but is not required for threat detection. Note that the results presented in this paper hold for any upper bound $\bar{\delta}_f$ to $|f(t)|$. In other words, $\bar{\delta}_f$ can be very large. Hence, a tight upper bound on $|f(t)|$ is not required. It is worth mentioning that \mathcal{Y} in (10) is an invariant subset for the closed-loop system (6) when $a_u(t) \equiv 0$ and $a_y(t) \equiv 0$. Given the values of δ_d and $\bar{\delta}_f$ in Assumptions 3 and 4, Υ can be derived based on A and ρ using, for example, Lyapunov algorithm [30]. ∇

This paper focuses on the following MITM cyber attacks: sensor replay attacks [11] and stealthy integrity attacks [13]–[15], [36]–[38]. Here, it is supposed that the attacker can disrupt all the sensor data transmission channels and all actuator data transmission channels. In particular, the advanced coordination of a_u and a_y can lead to the stealthy integrity attack such as the covert attack [36] and the perfectly undetectable attack [39]. Moreover, based on [11], [40], sensor replay attacks are also stealthy if the system is at the steady state when the attack occurs. More details on MITM cyber attacks are provided in Section III-B. Throughout the paper, we consider the case where only one attack type occurs during the detection and discrimination procedure.

B. Problem Statement

In this work, we use T_a to represent the unknown attack occurrence time and T_f to represent the time when any fault occurs. The scenario where $f(t) \equiv 0$, $a_u(t) \equiv 0$, and $a_y(t) \equiv 0$ is referred to as the nominal scenario, where $a_u(t) \neq 0$ and (or) $a_y(t) \neq 0$, and $f(t) \equiv 0$ for $t \geq T_a$ as the attack scenario, and the case where $a_u(t) \equiv 0$, $a_y(t) \equiv 0$, and $f(t) \neq 0$ for $t \geq T_f$ as the fault scenario. In addition, $a_u(t) \neq 0$ and (or) $a_y(t) \neq 0$, and $f(t) \neq 0$ for $t \geq \max\{T_a, T_f\}$ is referred to as the attack and fault scenario. For the attack and fault scenario, we consider that the attack and fault are simultaneously initiated at $T_{a,f}$. In this paper, we consider three threat scenarios: (i) a *cyber attack scenario* with a MITM attack, (ii) a *fault scenario* with one/multiple physical fault(s) and (iii) a *cyber attack and fault scenario* with a MITM attack and at least one physical fault. The problem considered in this paper is stated below.

Problem 1. For the system described by (6), we develop a threat detection and discrimination methodology that:

- (i) is able to indicate the occurrence of the considered threats and identify the threat scenario;
- (ii) has no effect on the control performance of the closed-loop system in the nominal and fault scenarios.

Problem 1(i) reflects the main detection and discrimination objective of this paper. Problem 1(ii) aims to eliminate the control performance degradation caused by the typical active diagnosis methodologies in such as [17], [19], [40]. The following sections present and discuss in detail the proposed detection and discrimination methodology.

III. SENSOR WATERMARK ARCHITECTURE

Based on the sensor additive watermark scheme in Fig. 1, this section presents the threat detection and discrimination architecture relying on an anomaly detector and suitably designed switching watermarks. We start by presenting the watermark architecture. In Fig. 1, $y_w \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ in the physical side and $\tilde{y}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ in the cyber side are the input and output of the sensor data transmission network respectively. The scheme comprises of a watermark generator \mathcal{W} and a remover \mathcal{Q} , generating signals $w \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ and $q \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$, respectively. Given watermarks w and q , y_w and \tilde{y}_w satisfy

$$y_w = y_p + w, \quad y_q = \tilde{y}_w - q. \quad (11)$$

To simplify the presentation, we unify \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} by introducing the index $h \in \{w, q\}$, where w and q correspond to the watermark generator and remover respectively.

A. Switching Watermark

The proposed watermark switches within the set $\{-\theta_1 - \theta_2, -\theta_1, \theta_1, \theta_1 + \theta_2\}$ at designed time instants, where $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ are vectors with positive elements. In particular, we consider two types of switches, which are referred to as outer and inner switches. The watermarks, corresponding to the outer and inner switches, are referred to as the *outer watermark trajectory* and *inner watermark trajectory* with magnitudes $|\theta_1 + \theta_2|$ and $|\theta_1|$, respectively. Moreover, a transition switch that transits from the outer watermark trajectory to the inner watermark trajectory is also taken into account.

We consider $N+1$ outer switches during one detection-and-discrimination time window where $N \in \mathbb{N}$ is bounded. For any $h \in \{w, q\}$, the outer switching time instants are represented by the following set:

$$S_h^o \triangleq \{t_{h,k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}}, \quad (12)$$

where $t_{h,k} \geq 0$ denotes the k -th outer switching time instant of the outer watermark trajectory $h \in \{w, q\}$. Then, the set of the transition switching time instants is given by

$$S_h^{tr} \triangleq \{\bar{t}_{h,k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}}, \quad (13)$$

where $\bar{t}_{h,k} > t_{h,k}$, and $\bar{t}_{h,k} - t_{h,k}$ is a constant for any k and h , representing the pulse duration of the outer watermark trajectory. In general, this pulse duration is very small such that the total energy of the outer watermark trajectory during one detection-and-discrimination time window can be ignored. In addition, we define the set of the inner switching time instants associated with the k -th outer switch for any $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$ as follows:

$$S_{h,k}^i \triangleq \{\bar{t}_{h,k} + \Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}} \cap (t_{h,k}, t_{h,k+1}), \quad (14)$$

Fig. 2. Illustrative example of the watermark scheme (16).

where Δt_k^j denotes the j th time seed associated with the k -th outer switch, and $\bar{t}_{h,k} + \Delta t_k^j$ denotes the j -th inner switching time instant. Then, the set of inner switching times for all inner watermark trajectories (i.e., for all $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$) is given by

$$S_h^i \triangleq \bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}} S_{h,k}^i. \quad (15)$$

Then, the watermark $h \in \{w, q\}$ is proposed as

$$h(t^+) = \begin{cases} -\text{sgn}(h(t))(\theta_1 + \theta_{2h}(t)), & \forall t \in S_h^o, \\ \text{sgn}(h(t))\theta_1, & \forall t \in S_h^{tr}, \\ -\text{sgn}(h(t))\theta_1, & \forall t \in S_h^i, \\ h(t), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $w(t_{w,0}) = q(t_{q,0})$, θ_{2w} and θ_{2q} are given by

$$\theta_{2w}(t) = H(|y_p(t)| - \Upsilon)\theta_2, \quad \theta_{2q}(t) = \theta_2, \quad (17)$$

with $H(\cdot)$ being the Heaviside function. The particularly designed θ_{2w} is introduced for the stealthy integrity attacks, which is discussed in detail in Section V. The values of θ_1 and θ_2 determine the switch synchronization between $w(t)$ and $q(t)$, and are discussed in Theorem 1 below. A simple example of (16) with $h(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is given in Fig. 2.

1) *Outer switches*: The outer switch occurring at $t \in S_h^o$, leads the outer watermark trajectory such that the watermark h lies in $\{-\theta_1 - \theta_2, \theta_1 + \theta_2\}$, which motivates their name. We use TPw and TPq to denote the triggering protocols for outer switches in \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} respectively. Then, these outer switches are triggered following certain specific protocols TPw of \mathcal{W} and TPq of \mathcal{Q} , which both rely on the system outputs. Moreover, TPw also includes some randomization, making it unpredictable. Further details of TPw and TPq are provided in the following section.

2) *Inner switches*: The inner switch occurring at $t \in S_h^i$, leads the inner watermark trajectory such that the watermark h falls in $\{-\theta_1, \theta_1\}$. Recalling $S_{h,k}^i$ in (14), the inner switches rely on a set of common time instants, namely $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}}$, used by both \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} . This common time instant set is referred to as a time seed, which is designed below.

3) *Watermark trajectory*: The jump at the outer switching time $t \in S_h^o$ is larger than that at the inner switching time $t \in S_h^i$ by design (16). This enables the outer switch of \mathcal{W} to trigger the switching protocol TPq and leads to a synchronized outer switch in \mathcal{Q} . On the other hand, by design (16), the inner

switch in \mathcal{W} cannot trigger TPq, and hence cannot lead to any asynchronous outer switch in \mathcal{Q} . The synchronization of switches is examined in Theorem 1 below.

Remark 3. The proposed watermark scheme does not degrade the control performance under nominal operation conditions since q is particularly designed to cancel out w deterministically, i.e., $y_q = y_p$ when $w = q$. This is a key advantage of the proposed watermark scheme compared with the input additive watermark approaches in [11], [40]. Moreover, compared with the statistical watermark in [25], the switching watermark allows the developed watermark methodology to effectively handle covert attacks [12], [13] and perfectly undetectable attacks [14]. In addition, the watermarks w and q in (16) are bounded, rather than monotonically increasing as in [1]. Furthermore, the sensor additive watermark can be regarded as a bounded disturbance, and cannot compromise system stability of most practical systems that are robust to bounded disturbances. This claim will be verified through hardware-in-the-loop experiments in future work. ∇

B. Attack Description under Watermark

In this subsection, the mathematical descriptions for some MITM attacks including sensor replay attacks and integrity attacks, are presented when \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are implemented.

1) *Sensor Attacks*: Following the proposed watermark scheme, in the presence of the attack, the received y_q satisfies:

$$y_q = y_p + w + a_y - q. \quad (18)$$

By taking watermarks w and q into account, the deviation between y_p and y_q , denoted as a_{eq} , i.e., $a_{eq} \triangleq y_q - y_p$, is considered as an equivalent attack to the sensor communication network. Then, in the attack scenario, a_{eq} can be written as:

$$a_{eq} = w + a_y - q. \quad (19)$$

For the replay attack, suppose that the attacker first records y_w starting at time $T_a - T_r$ and ending at time T_a , and then replays y_w starting at the same time. Then, for any $t \geq T_a$, the replay attack $a_y = y_w(t - T_r) - y_w(t)$ satisfies

$$a_y(t) = y_p(t - T_r) - y_p(t) + w(t - T_r) - w(t). \quad (20)$$

Hence, a_{eq} is bounded given the bounded y_p , w and q .

2) *Integrity Cyber Attacks*: We proceed with considering covert attacks [13], [36] and stealthy attacks [14], [15]. Consider the case of system (6) without any attack, given below:

$$\dot{x}_n = Ax_n + \rho(x_n, t) + B_f f + B_d d, \quad (21a)$$

$$y_{pn} = Cx_n + D_f f + D_d d, \quad y_{qn} = y_{pn}, \quad (21b)$$

where x_n , y_{pn} and y_{qn} represent the state, transmitted output and received output in the scenario without any attack, respectively. Then, the equivalent attack on the sensor communication network is defined based on the system (21) as

$$a_{eq} \triangleq y_q - y_{qn}. \quad (22)$$

The stealthy integrity attack aims to achieve $y_q = y_{qn}$ by coordinating a_u and a_y , which indicates that $y_{pn} = y_{qn} =$

$y_p + a_y$. It follows from (22) that $a_{eq} = y_p(t) + w(t) + a_y(t) - q(t) - y_{qn}(t)$ can be written as

$$a_{eq}(t) = w(t) - q(t). \quad (23)$$

Hence, a_{eq} is bounded given that w and q are bounded.

C. Anomaly Detector

The anomaly detector follows from commonly-used model-based approaches [32]. Specifically, it has the following form:

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = A\hat{x} + \rho(\hat{x}, t) - L(C\hat{x} - y_q), \quad (24a)$$

$$r = y_q - C\hat{x}, \quad (24b)$$

where $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state of the detector and $r \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is the *residual*. The gain matrix $L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_y}$ is chosen such that $A_r \triangleq A - LC$ is a Hurwitz matrix. Moreover, we let $S_f(s) \triangleq C(sI - A_r)^{-1}(B_f - LD_f) + D_f$ with convolution operator $M_{S_f}(T_f, t)$, $S_a(s) \triangleq -C(sI - A_r)^{-1}L + I$ with convolution operator $M_{S_a}(T_a, t)$, and $S_{af}(s) \triangleq C(sI - A_r)^{-1}[B_f - LD_f, -L] + [D_f, I]$ with convolution operator $M_{S_{af}}(T_{af}, t)$, represent the sensitivity functions to the fault, the attack and the attack and fault respectively. Then, L is assumed to be well-designed such that

$$\|S_f\|_- > 0, \|S_a\|_- > 0, \|S_{af}\|_- > 0, \quad (25)$$

respectively. Note that (25) is a common sensitivity requirement in fault diagnosis [32]. The specific design of L is out of the scope of this paper, and the interested reader can refer to [?], [29].

Recall that the designed watermarks $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ in (16) are bounded. It immediately follows that a_{eq} , given by (23), in the integrity attack case, and a_y , given by (20), in the sensor replay attack case are both bounded. Hence, a_{eq} defined in (19) and (23) are bounded, i.e., there exists some $\delta_a > 0$ such that

$$|a_{eq}(t)| \leq \delta_a, \quad \forall t \geq T_a. \quad (26)$$

Then, the following thresholds of the residual in the considered threat scenarios are obtained.

Lemma 2. *Let $\zeta > 0$ and $\mu > 0$ satisfy $|Ce^{A_r t}| \leq \zeta e^{-\mu t}$, and \bar{e}_0 satisfy $|\hat{x}(0) - x(0)| \leq \bar{e}_0$. Under Assumptions 1-4, the bounds of r are given below:*

(i) *In the nominal scenario, $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_d(t)$, where*

$$\bar{r}_d(t) \triangleq \left\| \frac{\zeta \|B_d - LD_d\| \delta_d}{\mu - \zeta \gamma} (1 - e^{-(\mu - \zeta \gamma)t}) + \|D_d\| \delta_d + \zeta \bar{e}_0 e^{-(\mu - \zeta \gamma)t} \right\|. \quad (27)$$

(ii) *In the fault scenario, $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_f(t)$, where $\bar{r}_f(t) = \bar{r}_d(t) + \bar{r}_{f0}(t)$ with \bar{r}_{f0} being given by*

$$\bar{r}_{f0}(t) \triangleq \|S_f(s)\|_\infty \bar{\delta}_f. \quad (28)$$

(iii) *In the attack scenario, $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_a(t)$ where $\bar{r}_a(t) \triangleq \bar{r}_d(t) + \bar{r}_{a0}(t)$ with \bar{r}_{a0} being given by*

$$\bar{r}_{a0}(t) \triangleq \|S_a(s)\|_\infty \delta_a. \quad (29)$$

Proof. It should be noted that in the integrity attack case, $r = y_q - C\hat{x} = y_{qn} - C\hat{x}$ which implicitly indicates that this detector is also suitable for detecting the integrity attack. We let $e \triangleq x_n - \hat{x}$ in the scenario with the integrity attack, and $e \triangleq x - \hat{x}$ in the scenario with the replay attack, to represent the estimation error. Then, r can be uniformly written as

$$\dot{e}_d = A_r e_d + \Delta \rho + (B_d - LD_d)d, \quad (30a)$$

$$r = r_d(t) + M_{S_f}(T_f, t)f + M_{S_a}(T_a, t)a_{eq}, \quad (30b)$$

where $r_d \triangleq Ce_d + D_d d$, $e_d(0) = x(0) - \hat{x}(0)$, $\Delta \rho = \rho(x_n, t) - \rho(\hat{x}, t)$ for the integrity attack case and $\Delta \rho = \rho(x, t) - \rho(\hat{x}, t)$ for the replay attack case. Then, under Assumption 3, it follows from [8] that the residual $r(t)$ in the nominal scenario is bounded by $\bar{r}_d(t)$. Moreover, based on the bounds of f in (9) and a_{eq} in (26), we can obtain $\|M_{S_f}(T_f, t)f\|_\infty \leq \|S_f\|_\infty \bar{\delta}_f$, $\|M_{S_a}(T_a, t)a_{eq}\|_\infty \leq \|S_a\|_\infty \delta_a$. Hence, the results follow. \square

Remark 4. *Recall the property for the linear time-invariant system given in Lemma 1. Using this property to (30b), the average energy of r is allowed to exceed any required threshold if the RMS of a_{eq} is well-tuned.*

The detection and discrimination strategy is based on the anomaly detector (24) and the time-varying thresholds $\bar{r}_d(t)$, $\bar{r}_f(t)$ and $\bar{r}_a(t)$. To this end, we let $T_d \geq \min\{T_f, T_a\}$ be the time of threat detection, and T_{\max} be the finite *standby time* which is the maximum required time to achieve threat discrimination after threat detection. The proposed strategy, referred to as the *bi-layer decision strategy* hereafter, is described below:

- 1) *Layer-1:* If $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_d(t)$ at some time $t = T_d$, then a threat is detected at T_d . Otherwise, no threat is detected;
- 2) *Layer-2:* Given $\|r(T_d)\| > \bar{r}_d(T_d)$ in *Layer-1*, then,
 - if $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_f(t)$ for all $t \in (T_d, T_d + T_{\max}]$, then the fault scenario is identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$;
 - if $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_f(t)$ at some finite time $t \in (T_d, T_d + T_{\max}]$ and $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_a(t)$ for all $t \in (T_d, T_d + T_{\max}]$, then the attack scenario is identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$;
 - if $\|r(t)\| \geq \bar{r}_a(t)$ at some finite time $t = t_a \in (T_d, T_d + T_{\max}]$, then the attack and fault scenario is identified at t_a .

Remark 5. *The value of T_{\max} is an estimate of the time length from the attack occurrence to the outer switch synchronization between \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} , which is discussed in detail in Section V. From the above bi-layer decision strategy, the decision about the occurring threat scenario can be made before $T_d + T_{\max}$. Hence, $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ start their switches from the initial time and can stop after $T_d + T_{\max}$. The interruption of the switches avoids the asynchronization between $w(t)$ and $q(t)$, thereby alleviating its negative effects on the control performance. In addition, the threat detection and discrimination based on the anomaly detector (24) and the bi-layer decision strategy is an automated decision-making process rather than an autonomous execution process, which makes decisions based on the predefined principle using the magnitude relation between the residual and the predefined thresholds. ∇*

Remark 6. Compared with the methodology in [6], [7] which includes a bank of detectors and thresholds, the detection and discrimination methodology in this paper is simple since only one detector with multiple thresholds is used. Another significant benefit is that the proposed detection and discrimination methodology works effectively for threat scenarios with perfectly stealthy attacks such as replay attacks and covert attacks [14]. In contrast, the methodology in [6], [7] cannot identify the threat scenarios with these perfectly stealthy attacks. ∇

IV. DESIGN OF WATERMARK SCHEMES

In this section, we present the designs of the switching protocols TPw and TPq and the time seeds $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$.

A. Switching Protocol Design

One aim of the TPw and TPq is to guarantee that the outer switches in \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are synchronized in the nominal and fault scenarios, i.e., $S_w^o = S_q^o$. Moreover, the inner switches of \mathcal{W} do not trigger TPq and thus do not induce any outer switch in \mathcal{Q} . In addition, TPw and TPq include some randomization to introduce some confidentiality against the attacker. The approach to design TPw and TPq is presented below. The TPq of the remover \mathcal{Q} is first proposed as follows:

$$\text{TPq: } t_{q,k} \triangleq \inf_{t \geq t_{q,k-1}} \left\{ t \mid |y_q(t) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+)| \geq \eta \right\},$$

$$t_{q,0} = 0, \forall k \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,N]}, \quad (31)$$

where $\eta > 0$ is a design parameter. Note that the switching condition (31) in TPq may be triggered by both $y_p(t)$ and $w(t)$, through their effect on $y_q(t)$. Hence, for the synchronization purpose, the TPw has two tasks: **(a)** synchronizing with the spontaneous switches in \mathcal{Q} due to the variations of $y_p(t)$ and $w(t)$, and **(b)** enforcing a new switch in \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} at random time to induce confidentiality. Corresponding to tasks **(a)** and **(b)**, we propose two mechanisms for enabling switching. In particular, we consider two time instants given by

$$\hat{t}_{w,k} \triangleq \inf_{t \geq t_{w,k-1} + \alpha} \left\{ t \mid |y_q(t) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+)| \geq \eta \right\}, \quad (32a)$$

$$t'_{w,k} \triangleq t_{w,k-1} + \alpha_k, \forall k \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,N]}, \quad (32b)$$

where $\alpha < \alpha_k < \bar{\alpha}$ is randomly generated at the previous switching time $t_{w,k-1}$ with α and $\bar{\alpha}$ being positive constants, the design of which is associated with the time seeds (see Section IV-B below). Then, TPw for any $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$ is designed as follows

$$\text{TPw: } t_{w,k} \triangleq \min \{t'_{w,k}, \hat{t}_{w,k}\}, t_{w,0} = 0. \quad (33)$$

The switching protocols in (31) and (32a) cannot be predicted by the attacker since their triggering conditions are affected by the unpredictable disturbance d through y_q in (32a). In addition, the switch protocol in (32b) is also unpredictable due to the random value of α_k used for generating the switching time $t'_{w,k}$. Hence, the TPq and TPw, characterized by (31) and (33) respectively, cannot be predicted by the attacker, thereby inducing confidentiality. ∇

Note that TPq (31) and TPw (32a) cannot be implemented directly since $y_p(t_{q,k-1})$ is inaccessible from the cyber side, and $y_q(t)$ is inaccessible from the physical side. The implementable equivalent forms of TPq (31) and TPw (32a) are specified below. Note that $y_q(t) = \tilde{y}_w(t^+) - q(t)$.

Lemma 3. The switch triggering conditions (31) and (32a) can be equivalently written as

$$t_{q,k} = \inf_{t \geq t_{q,k-1}} \left\{ t \mid |\tilde{y}_w(t^+) - \tilde{y}_w(t_{q,k-1}^+) - q(t) + q(t_{q,k-1}^+)| \geq \eta \right\}, \quad (34a)$$

$$\hat{t}_{w,k} = \inf_{t \geq t_{w,k-1} + \alpha} \left\{ t \mid |y_p(t) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+)| \geq \eta \right\}, \quad (34b)$$

for any $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,N]}$, where $t_{q,0} = 0$ and $\hat{t}_{w,0} = 0$.

Proof. The signal y_q in the cyber side is written as $y_q(t) = \tilde{y}_w(t^+) - q(t)$. Then, it follows that $y_q(t) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+) = \tilde{y}_w(t^+) - q(t) - (\tilde{y}_w(t_{q,k-1}^+) - q(t_{q,k-1}^+))$. Hence, the equivalent form (34a) is obtained. Note that before the switch at $t_{w,k}$, i.e., $t \leq t_{w,k}$, $y_q(t) = y_p(t)$ and $t_{w,k-1} = t_{q,k-1}$. Then, $y_q(t) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+) = y_p(t) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+)$. Hence, (34b) is obtained. \square

We proceed with analyzing the synchronization of the outer switches in \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} in the theorem below.

Theorem 1. Consider the networked control system (6) with disturbance d and potential fault f satisfying Assumptions 3 and 4 respectively, and the watermark schemes with watermarks $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ described by (16) and switching protocols (31)–(33). If θ_1 , θ_2 , and η are designed such that

$$|2\theta_1 + \theta_2| \geq \eta + 2\Upsilon, \quad (35a)$$

$$|\theta_2| < \eta - 2\Upsilon, \quad (35b)$$

$$|2\theta_1| < \eta - 2\Upsilon, \quad (35c)$$

where Υ is given in (10), then in the nominal and fault cases, **(a)** any outer switch in \mathcal{W} induces an outer switch in \mathcal{Q} , i.e.,

$$|y_q(t) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+)| \geq \eta, \forall t \in S_w^o. \quad (36)$$

(b) the transit and inner switches in \mathcal{W} do not induce any outer switch in \mathcal{Q} , i.e.,

$$|y_q(t) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+)| < \eta, \forall t \in S_w^{tr} \cup S_w^i. \quad (37)$$

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

Remark 7. As shown in Theorem 1, in the nominal and fault scenarios, the outer switch synchronization between the generator \mathcal{W} and the remover \mathcal{Q} is guaranteed by the design of θ_1 , θ_2 and η in (35). In particular, (35a) guarantees that any outer switch in \mathcal{W} induces an outer switch in \mathcal{Q} , (35b) guarantees that the transit switches in \mathcal{W} do not induce any outer switch in \mathcal{Q} , and (35c) ensures that the inner switches in \mathcal{W} do not induce any outer switch in \mathcal{Q} . ∇

Remark 8. Note that α_k in (32b) determines the lower bound of outer switching frequencies of $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ provided that $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ are synchronized. This is inferred from the upper bound of α_k and TPw (33). By design, η , jointly selected with θ_1 and θ_2 to satisfy (35), is used to ensure outer switching synchronization between $w(t)$ and $q(t)$. ∇

B. Time Seed Design

In this subsection, we present suitable design conditions for the time seeds $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ for any $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$. To this end, we move our focus on the inner watermark trajectory $h(t)$ in the time interval $(t_{h,k}, t_{h,k+1}]$, denoted by $h_k(t)$. Without loss of generality, we consider any two time seeds $k_1 \neq k_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$ and some $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $(t_{k_1}^h, t_{k_2}^h] \triangleq (t_{h,k_1} - \varepsilon, t_{h,k_1+1} - \varepsilon] \cap (t_{h,k_2}, t_{h,k_2+1}] \neq \emptyset$. The difference between the inner watermark trajectories h_{k_1} and h_{k_2} is defined as follows:

$$\Delta h_{k_1, k_2}(t, \varepsilon) \triangleq h_{k_1}(t - \varepsilon) - h_{k_2}(t), \quad \forall t \in (t_{k_1}^h, t_{k_2}^h]. \quad (38)$$

Then, the requirements for the time seed are given below.

Design Condition 1. *The time seed $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ for $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$ satisfies the following properties:*

- (i) *For any $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}$, there exists a time $t \in (t_{k_1}^h, t_{k_2}^h]$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ such that*

$$\|\Delta h_{k_1, k_2}(t, \varepsilon)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} \geq \Delta \bar{h}(t), \quad (39)$$

where $\Delta \bar{h}(\cdot)$ is an adaptive threshold and specified later.

- (ii) *Confidential information is embedded in $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$.*

Design Condition 1 imposes two requirements on the design of the time seeds. In particular, Design Condition 1(i) ensures that the RMS of the difference between any inner trajectories is sufficiently large, which, based on Lemma 1, leads to a sufficiently large detection residual r when evaluated using average energy. As a result, the second layer of the *bi-layer decision strategy* can be used for handling the cyber attack scenarios, which is discussed in detail in Section V. The confidentiality of the time seed is ensured by Design Condition 1(ii). An approach to design the time seed satisfying Design Condition 1 is presented in Section VI.

V. DETECTABILITY AND DISCRIMINATION ABILITY

In this section, we analyze the detection and discrimination abilities of the developed switching watermark methodology and rigorously characterize the class of physical faults and MITM cyber attacks that can be detected and discriminated. We first present a result for the MITM cyber attacks in the following theorem.

Theorem 2. *Consider system (6) and anomaly detector (24) with thresholds $\bar{r}_d(t)$, $\bar{r}_f(t)$ and $\bar{r}_a(t)$ in (27)-(29) and let Assumptions 1-4 hold. Consider the watermark scheme (16) with TPq (31) and TPw (32)-(33), and θ_1 , θ_2 , and η satisfying (35). Given the standby time T_{\max} , then*

- (i) *the fault scenario can be identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$ if there exist $T_d > T_f$ and $\kappa > 0$ such that*

$$\|f(T_d)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} > \frac{2\sqrt{T_d - T_f}\bar{r}_d(T_d)}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_f\|_-}. \quad (40)$$

- (ii) *the attack scenario can be identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$ if there exist $T_d > T_a$ and $\kappa > 0$ such that*

$$\|a_{eq}(T_d)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} > \frac{\sqrt{T_d - T_a}(2\bar{r}_d(T_d) + \bar{r}_{f0}(T_d))}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_a\|_-}. \quad (41)$$

- (iii) *the fault and attack scenario can be detected at T_d and discriminated at t_a if there exists $\kappa > 0$ such that $f(t)$ and $a_{eq}(t)$ satisfy*

$$\|[f^T(T_d), a_{eq}^T(T_d)]^T\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} > \frac{2\sqrt{T_d - T_{af}}\bar{r}_d(T_d)}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}, \quad (42a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \|[f^T(t_a), a_{eq}^T(t_a)]^T\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} \\ & > \frac{\sqrt{t_a - T_{af}}(2\bar{r}_d(t_a) + \bar{r}_{a0}(t_a))}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}. \end{aligned} \quad (42b)$$

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

Theorem 2 characterizes the fault, the attack and the fault and attack scenarios that can be detected and discriminated in the considered finite time interval, using the *bi-layer decision strategy*. We further characterize the detectability and discrimination ability for replay attacks and integrity attacks, by analyzing the synchronization between w and q .

A. Ability Analysis for Replay Attacks

The replay attack scenario and the replay attack and fault scenario are taken into account in this subsection. A general replay attack setup is considered: the replay attack occurs between two outer switches of \mathcal{W} , i.e., $T_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k}]$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 2}$, and its recording time length is T_r . Let k_0 represent the outer switches of \mathcal{W} that the recording procedure covers. Then, a result regarding the outer switches in \mathcal{Q} is presented below.

Proposition 1. *Consider the system (6) and let Assumptions 1-4 hold. Consider the watermark scheme (16) with TPq (31) and TPw (32)-(33), θ_1 , θ_2 , and η satisfying (35). In the presence of a replay attack given by (20) at $T_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k}]$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 2}$, with the recording time length T_r satisfying*

$$T_r > \max_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,N]}} \{\alpha_k\}, \quad (43)$$

where α_k is given in (32b), if for some $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| q(t_{q,k-k_0+i}^+) - q(t_{q,k-k_0+i} + T_r) \right. \\ & \left. + H(i)(q(t_{q,k+i-1}^+) - q(t_{q,k+i-1} - T_r)) \right| \geq |2\theta_1 + \theta_2|, \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

where $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside function, then the outer switches in \mathcal{Q} satisfy

$$t_{q,k+i} = t_{q,k-k_0+i} + T_r. \quad (45)$$

Additionally, if $t_{w,k-k_0+i} + T_r \neq t_{w,k+i}$ for some $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$, then the outer switches of \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are asynchronized at $t_{w,k-k_0+i} + T_r$.

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

Remark 9. *Some special cases that satisfy condition (44) are discussed below.*

- (i) *The first case is $i = 0$. In this case, (44) becomes*

$$\left| q(t_{q,k-k_0}^+) - q(t_{q,k-k_0} + T_r) \right| \geq |2\theta_1 + \theta_2|. \quad (46)$$

Given $q(t)$ in (16), this condition is equivalent to

$$q(t_{q,k-k_0}^+)q(t_{q,k-k_0} + T_r) < 0. \quad (47)$$

(ii) When $i \geq 1$, if

$$q(t_{q,k+i-1}^+) = q(t_{q,k+i-1}^+ - T_r), \quad (48)$$

then (44) can be written as

$$\left| q(t_{q,k-k_0+i}^+) - q(t_{q,k-k_0+i} + T_r) \right| \geq |2\theta_1 + \theta_2|. \quad (49)$$

The above two cases are also verified in the simulation section in Section VII. However, various other cases can meet condition (44). ∇

The detectability and discrimination ability for replay attacks is given below.

Proposition 2. Consider the system (6) and the anomaly detector (24) with thresholds $\bar{r}_d(t)$, $\bar{r}_f(t)$ and $\bar{r}_a(t)$ in (27)–(29) and let Assumptions 1–4 hold. Consider the watermark scheme (16) with TPq (31) and TPw (32)–(33), θ_1 , θ_2 , and η satisfying (35). Consider the case that the replay attack occurs at $T_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k}]$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 2}$ and $t_{w,k-k_0+i} + T_r \neq t_{w,k+i}$ for some $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$. Then, the replay attack and fault scenario is detected at T_d and discriminated at t_a where

$$T_d, t_a \in (t_{q,k+i}, t_{q,k+i+1}], \quad (50)$$

if $\Delta\bar{q}(t)$ and $f(t)$ satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{(\Delta\bar{q}(T_d) - 2\kappa\Upsilon)^2 + \|f(T_d)\|_{\mathbb{R},\kappa}^2} \\ & > \frac{2\sqrt{T_d - T_{af}}\bar{r}_d(T_d)}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}, \end{aligned} \quad (51a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{(\Delta\bar{q}(t_a) - 2\kappa\Upsilon)^2 + \|f(t_a)\|_{\mathbb{R},\kappa}^2} \\ & > \frac{\sqrt{t_a - T_{af}}(2\bar{r}_d(t_a) + \bar{r}_{a0}(t_a))}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}. \end{aligned} \quad (51b)$$

The standby time is $T_{\max} = (i+2)\bar{\alpha}$. Moreover, in the attack scenario, the replay attack can be identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$ if there exists some time T_d satisfying (50) such that

$$\Delta\bar{q}(T_d) \geq \frac{\sqrt{T_d - T_{af}}(2\bar{r}_d(T_d) + \bar{r}_{f0}(T_d))}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-} + 2\kappa\Upsilon. \quad (52)$$

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

Remark 10. Consider the time-delay-switch (TDS) attack introduced in [41], in which the attack is a switch action “Off/Delay-by- T_r ” where $T_r : t \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ takes a random value at t (T_r is used here to maintain notation consistency with the replay attack case). Compared with the considered replay attack with a fixed T_r , the delay caused by the TDS attack randomly varies with time. For such an attack, the same detection and discrimination abilities as the replay attack in Proposition 2 can be derived if $T_r(t)$ satisfies (43) for all $t \geq 0$ and if $t_{w,k-k_0+i} + T_r(t_{q,k+i}) \neq t_{w,k+i}$ for some $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 2}$. The intuitive reason is that under the condition (43), as derived in (45), $t_{q,k+i} = t_{w,k-k_0+i} + T_r(t_{q,k+i})$. ∇

B. Ability Analysis for Integrity Attacks

In this subsection, the detection and discrimination abilities of the proposed scheme are analyzed by studying the outer switch asynchronization and the equivalent attack a_{eq} in the stealthy integrity attack case. Recalling the attack described by (23), a result regarding the outer switch asynchronization in the stealthy attack case is presented below.

Proposition 3. Consider the system (6) and let Assumptions 1–4 hold. Consider the watermark schemes with $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ in (16) and switch protocols (31)–(33). In the presence of a stealthy integrity attack given in (23) at $T_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k-1} + \alpha_k]$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$, the outer switches between \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{W} are asynchronized at τ_a if

$$|y_p(\tau_a) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+)| > \eta, \quad (53a)$$

$$y_p(\tau_a) \notin \mathcal{Y}, \quad (53b)$$

for some $\tau_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k-1} + \alpha_k]$. \blacksquare

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

The conditions in (53) suggest that \mathcal{W} has an outer switch at τ_a , whereas \mathcal{Q} does not. It should be noted that the opposite case where \mathcal{W} has an outer switch whereas \mathcal{Q} not, is impossible due to the restriction for θ_1 and θ_2 in (35a) and θ_{2w} in (17). The detectability and discrimination ability for the stealthy attack case is given in the following proposition.

Proposition 4. Consider the system (6) and the anomaly detector (24) with thresholds $\bar{r}_d(t)$, $\bar{r}_f(t)$ and $\bar{r}_a(t)$ in (27)–(29) and let Assumptions 1–4 hold. Consider the watermark scheme (16) with TPq (31) and TPw (32)–(33), θ_1 , θ_2 , and η satisfying (35). Consider a stealthy integrity attack at $T_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k}]$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$ satisfying (53) at $\tau_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k-1} + \alpha_k]$. Then, the integrity attack and fault scenario is detected at T_d and discriminated at t_a where

$$T_d, t_a \in (t_{w,k-1}, t_{w,k}], \quad (54)$$

if $\Delta\bar{w}(t)$ and $f(t)$ satisfy

$$\sqrt{\Delta\bar{w}^2(T_d) + \|f(T_d)\|_{\mathbb{R},\kappa}^2} \geq \frac{2\sqrt{T_d - T_{af}}\bar{r}_d(T_d)}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}, \quad (55a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{\Delta\bar{w}^2(t_a) + \|f(t_a)\|_{\mathbb{R},\kappa}^2} \\ & \geq \frac{\sqrt{t_a - T_{af}}(2\bar{r}_d(t_a) + \bar{r}_{a0}(t_a))}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}. \end{aligned} \quad (55b)$$

The standby time satisfies $T_{\max} = \bar{\alpha}$. Moreover, in the attack scenario, the integrity attack is identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$ if there exists some time T_d satisfying (54) such that

$$\Delta\bar{w}(T_d) \geq \frac{\sqrt{T_d - T_{af}}(2\bar{r}_d(T_d) + \bar{r}_{f0}(T_d))}{\sqrt{\kappa}\|S_{af}\|_-}. \quad (56)$$

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

VI. FEASIBLE LORENZ TIME SEED DESIGN

In this section, we present an approach for designing the time seed satisfying Design Condition 1. The time seed design procedure is first presented and Design Condition 1 is then verified.

Fig. 3. The graph of the map g on Σ and the orbit $\{\xi^0, \xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3\}$.

A. Lorenz Time Seed Design

We start by presenting some preliminaries of the Lorenz system [42] given as follows

$$\dot{\rho} = 10(\xi - \rho), \quad (57a)$$

$$\dot{\xi} = 28\rho - \xi - \rho v, \quad (57b)$$

$$\dot{v} = \rho\xi - 8/3v. \quad (57c)$$

Consider a square Σ where

$$\Sigma \triangleq \{\rho, \xi, v \mid |\rho| \leq 20, |\xi| \leq 20, \xi \neq 0, v = 27\}, \quad (58)$$

and the map g that maps the line ξ on Σ to the line ρ on Σ . Also, let g^n denote the n -th iteration of g , i.e., g^n is the n -fold composition of g . Given a $\xi^0 \in \mathbb{R}$, the orbit of ξ^0 is the sequence $\{\xi^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ where $\xi^j = g^j(\xi^0)$. For intuition, this orbit is depicted in Fig. 3 for $n = 3$.

We proceed with designing the time seed $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ based on the Lorenz system (57). Inspired by [43], the procedure proposed in this paper to generate the feasible Lorenz time seed includes four modules (see Fig. 4): a key module, a real number generator module, a Lorenz system module and a time seed generator module. In particular, the set of secret keys is selected first and given as follows:

$$\text{Key} \triangleq \{\text{key}_k \in \mathbb{Q}_{\geq 0} \mid \text{key}_{k_1} \neq \text{key}_{k_2}, \forall k_1 \neq k_2, \\ k, k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}\}. \quad (59)$$

The algorithm to select Key is discussed below. Given the above Key , a set of initial conditions, denoted as $\{\xi_k^0\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}}$, is produced by the following real number generator:

$$\xi_k^0 = ((\text{key}_k + 1) * \pi) \bmod 40 - 20, \text{key}_k \in \text{Key}. \quad (60)$$

By iterating based on the function g of the Lorenz system (57), for each initial condition $\xi_k^0 \in \{\xi_k^0\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}}$, an orbit of ξ_k^0 can be calculated and given as the sequence $\{\xi_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ (see the orbit in Fig. 3). Then, the time seed generator is designed as follows:

$$\Delta t_k^j \triangleq \frac{\sum_{l=0}^j (\xi_k^l + 20)}{\lambda}, \forall j \in \mathbb{N}, k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}, \quad (61)$$

where $\lambda > 0$ enables to adjust the length of $\Delta t_k^{j+1} - \Delta t_k^j$.

Remark 11. The algorithm to generate the sequence $\{\xi_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ is presented below. Note that the function g is not explicitly known and thus, the sequence $\{\xi_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ cannot be calculated straightforwardly based on g . For a given ξ_k^0 , we construct $\zeta_{0,k} \triangleq [-20, \xi_k^0, 27]^T$ to be the k -th initial condition for

Fig. 4. Schematic procedure to generate the Lorenz time seed.

the Lorenz system (57). Let $\phi_\rho(t, \zeta_0)$, $\phi_\xi(t, \zeta_0)$ and $\phi_v(t, \zeta_0)$ denote the analytical solutions of ρ , ξ and v , respectively, at time t for the Lorenz system (57) starting from the initial condition ζ_0 . Then, by collecting the time instants that the trajectory of the Lorenz system with the initial condition $\zeta_{0,k}$ intersects the surface Σ in (58), we can define a time set $\Xi_k \triangleq \{t_k^1, t_k^2, t_k^3, \dots\}$, given as follows:

$$\Xi_k \triangleq \{t_k^1 < t_k^2 < t_k^3 < \dots, \mid \phi_v(t_k^l, \zeta_{0,k}) = 27, \\ |\phi_\rho(t_k^l, \zeta_{0,k})| < 20, \forall l \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}\}. \quad (62)$$

Thus, ξ_k^l is calculated as follows:

$$\xi_k^l = \phi_\xi(t_k^l, \zeta_{0,k}), \forall t_k^l \in \Xi_k, l \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}. \quad (63)$$

B. Verification of Design Condition 1(i)

The following theorem demonstrates that Design Condition 1(i) in Section IV-B is satisfied when the parameters of the time seed generator (61) are properly selected.

Theorem 3. Consider the Lorenz time seed $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (61) characterized by Key in (59), the initial condition set $\{\xi_k^0\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}}$ in (60), and the inner watermark trajectory $h_k(t)$ (16). Then, if Key is selected such that

$$\xi_{k_1}^0 \notin \{\xi_{k_2}^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}, \forall k_1 \neq k_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}, \quad (64)$$

the value of λ is selected such that for the given evaluation time length κ of RMS,

$$\Delta t_k^{j+1} - \Delta t_k^j = \frac{\xi_k^j}{\lambda} \geq \kappa, \forall j \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (65)$$

and θ_1 is selected such that for some $t \in (t_{k_1}^h, t_{k_2}^h]$,

$$|\theta_1| \geq \sqrt{\frac{\Delta \bar{h}(t)}{2}}, \quad (66)$$

where $\Delta \bar{h}$ is given by (39), then Design Condition 1(i) is satisfied.

Proof. The proof can be found in the Appendix. \square

Remark 12. The intuition behind Theorem 3 is as follows. The design (64) ensures $\Delta h_{k_1, k_2}(t, \varepsilon) \neq 0$, and (65) that the time length between any two inner switch trajectories is sufficiently large such that the generalized cross-correlation¹ $\int_{t-\kappa}^t h_{k_1}(\tau - \varepsilon) h_{k_2}(\tau) d\tau = 0$. With the above design, the RMS of the difference between any two inner switch trajectories, i.e., $\|\Delta h_{k_1, k_2}(t, \varepsilon)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}$, determined by the RMS of the watermark $h(t)$ (see the proof in the Appendix), can be easily adjusted by θ_1 to satisfy Design Condition 1(i). ∇

¹See the definition of the generalized cross-correlation in [44].

C. Verification of Design Condition 1(ii)

The expanding property of the map g guarantees that Design Condition 1(ii) is satisfied. The following lemma describes the expanding property of g .

Lemma 4 (Expanding Property). [42], [45] *Let $v \in (0, 20)$ and $\xi^0 \in [-20, 20]$. Given any $\epsilon > 0$, for any $\xi_1^0, \xi_2^0 \in [-20, 20]$, $\xi_1^0 \neq \xi_2^0$, $|\xi_1^0 - \xi_2^0| < \epsilon$ and $|\xi_2^0 - \xi^0| < \epsilon$, it holds that $|g(\xi_1^0) - g(\xi_2^0)| \geq \sqrt{2}|\xi_1^0 - \xi_2^0|$. Moreover, there exists some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $|g^n(\xi_1^0) - g^n(\xi_2^0)| \geq 2v$. ■*

The time seeds $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ are confidential and cannot be inferred by the attacker provided that the defender maintains the *Key* set secure. This can be viewed from Lemma 4, which shows that any difference between the *Key* sequence obtained by the attacker and the true *Key* sequence results in a significant deviation of the time seeds generated in (61). Specifically, for the k th outer switch, ξ_k^l generated by the Lorenz system (57) significantly deviates from its true value if the attacker initiates from any different ξ_k^0 . This leads to significantly different time seeds generated based on ξ_k^l in (61). Hence, the time seeds generated based on the Lorenz system satisfy Design Condition 1(ii).

VII. SIMULATION

In this section, a simulation based on the system described by (6) is presented. The system matrices are given as follows:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -3.50 & -0.20 & 0 \\ -0.07 & -4.79 & 1 \\ -0.09 & -2.79 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_f = \begin{bmatrix} 0.05I_3, & \begin{bmatrix} -1.67 & 0 \\ 0 & -1.737 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.9 \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$C = [I_2 \ 0], \quad D_f = [0 \ I_2], \quad B_d = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0.12 & 0 \\ 0.21 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad D_d = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.1 \\ 0 & 0.4 \end{bmatrix},$$

where the pair (C, A) is observable. Moreover, the nonlinearity is given by $\rho(x) = [\sin x_1, \cos(x_1 + x_2), 0.2 \sin(x_3)]$, where the Lipschitz constant is $\gamma = 1.42$. Hence, Assumptions 1 and 2 are satisfied. To satisfy Assumptions 3 and 4, we set $|d(t)| \leq 5$ and $|f(t)| \leq 170$ respectively. Thus, we select $\delta_d = 5$ and $\bar{\delta}_f = 178$. Moreover, relaxed bounds of a_{eq} and y_p are used by selecting $\delta_a = 200$ in (26) and $\Upsilon = 60$ in (10).

Regarding the anomaly detector (24), the gain L is given by $L = [L_1, L_2]$ with $L_1 = [1.550, -0.051, 0.022]^T$ and $L_2 = [0.9998, -0.905, 0.203]^T$. Then, $\bar{r}_d(t)$, $\bar{r}_{f0}(t)$ and $\bar{r}_{a0}(t)$ are given as $\bar{r}_d(t) = 21.439 - 14.320e^{-0.194t}$, $\bar{r}_{f0}(t) = 24$, and $\bar{r}_{a0}(t) = 66.34$.

The design parameters for outer and inner switches are given below. Regarding the triggering protocols TPw and TPq, $\eta = 480$ and α_k in TPw satisfies $2 = \underline{\alpha} \leq \alpha_k \leq \bar{\alpha} = 10$. To satisfy the derived conditions in Theorem 1, $\theta_1 = 80$ and $\theta_2 = 332$.

We first verify Theorem 3 by giving the time length of the RMS $\kappa = 2$, and $\Delta \bar{h}(t) = 100$. By selecting ξ_k^0 for $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,150]}$, $\lambda = 10$ and $\theta_1 = 80[1, 1]^T$ respectively meeting (64), (65) and (66), we generate $N = 150$ time sequences $\{\Delta t_k^j\}_{k \in [0,150]}$ for the inner switches. The RMS of the difference between some inner switch trajectories is shown in Fig. 5. It verifies that the design based on Theorem 3 can guarantee that $\|\Delta h_{k_1, k_2}(t, \delta)\|_{R, \kappa}$ for any k_1 and k_2 can exceed $\Delta \bar{h}(t)$, i.e., meets Design Condition 1(i).

For the simulation setup, $d(t)$ is given by $d(t) = [2 \sin(50t), d_1(t)]^T$, where d_1 is randomly selected at each

Fig. 5. RMS of the difference between some inner switch trajectories.

time instant from the uniform distribution $[-2, 2]$. A physical fault $f(t) = [f_1(t), f_2(t), f_3(t)]^T$ occurs at $T_f = 25$ s with $f_1 = [120 \cos(2t), 0, 0]^T$, $f_2 = [0, 120 \sin(5t), 0]^T$ and $f_3 = [0, -54 \sin(4t)]^T$. The detection and discrimination results in the fault scenario are shown in Fig. 6. The residual r exceeds \bar{r}_d at 26s, and remains below \bar{r}_f for all the simulation time. Based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, a threat is detected at 26s and is identified as a fault if the threshold does not exceed \bar{r}_a before $26s + T_{\max}$. The standby time T_{\max} required to identify this physical fault is given later. The outer switches of w and q in Fig. 6 remain synchronized after the occurrence of the fault, which verifies Theorem 1 in terms that no outer switch synchronization is triggered in the fault scenario.

Fig. 6. Detection and discrimination results, and the watermarks in the fault scenario.

1) *Replay Attack Setup*: The recording procedure initiates at $T_a - T_r = 7$ s and ends at $T_a = 32$ s, and then the replaying procedure starts at T_a . Hence, $T_r = 25$ s satisfies (43) in

Fig. 7. Detection and discrimination results, and the watermarks in the replay attack scenario and the fault and replay attack scenario.

Fig. 8. Discrimination result of the fault discrimination scheme for the replay attack using the method in [6].

Proposition 1. In addition, based on Proposition 2, the minimal T_{\max} required to identify the threat type is obtained when $i = 0$, i.e., $T_{\max} = 2\bar{\alpha} = 20\text{s}$.

The detection and discrimination results in the replay attack scenario and the fault and attack scenario are illustrated in Fig. 7. It shows that in the replay attack scenario, r exceeds $\bar{r}_d(t)$ and $\bar{r}_f(t)$ at about 32.8s and 32.9s respectively. In the fault and replay attack scenario, r exceeds $\bar{r}_d(t)$ and $\bar{r}_f(t)$ at about 26s and 32.8s respectively. The maximum time length T_{\max} is marked by magenta colour in both Figs. 6 and 7.

Consider all the threat scenarios composed of the fault and the replay attack. In the fault scenario, from Fig. 6 and based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, a threat is detected at $T_d = 26\text{s}$ and then identified as a fault at $T_d + T_{\max} = 46\text{s}$. In the replay attack scenario, from the left two sub-figures of Fig. 7 and based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, a threat is detected at $T_d = 32.8\text{s}$, and identified as an attack at $T_d + T_{\max} = 52.8\text{s}$. Moreover, in the fault and replay attack scenario, from the right two sub-figures of Fig. 7, a threat is detected at $T_d = 26\text{s}$, and is identified as a fault and attack scenario at about 38s.

The watermarks $w(t)$ and $q(t)$ in Fig. 7 show that their outer switches are synchronized before 32.8s but are asynchronous afterwards. In addition, the two outer switches after T_a (or T_{af}) are examples satisfying condition (44) in Proposition 1, corresponding to the discussed special cases in Remark 9. The black circles correspond to the case (i), showing the situation in which (47) is not met and thus, no outer switch occurs in \mathcal{Q} at $t_{q,1} + T_r$. The green diamonds illustrate an example that the outer switch condition in case (ii) is satisfied. Specifically, $q(t_{q,4}^+) = q(t_{q,4}^+ - T_r)$ and $q(t_{q,2}^+) - q(t_{q,2}^+ + T_r) = 2\theta_1 + \theta_2$.

As a comparison with the existing works on the threat discrimination, we present the discrimination result for the replay attack scenario using the passive method in [6]. An attack discrimination scheme and a fault discrimination scheme are included in the passive method, and based on the decision principle, the replay attack is discriminated if the residual of the fault discrimination scheme exceeds the threshold. The residuals and the thresholds of the fault discrimination scheme in [6] are shown in Fig. 8, which shows that the both residuals do not exceed their counter thresholds, demonstrating that the passive method [6] cannot identify the replay attack.

2) Stealthy Integrity Attack Setup: The stealthy integrity attack starts at $T_a = 28\text{s}$. The attack signal is constructed based on [15] with the attack model being given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= (A_p + [B_p, 0] F_a) z + [B_p, 0] L_a \psi(t), \\ [a_u^T, a_y^T]^T &= F_a z + L_a \psi(t), \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 9. Detection and discrimination results, and the watermarks in the integrity attack scenario and the fault and integrity attack scenario.

where the matrices F_a and L_a are calculated based on [15]. Moreover, $\psi = [\psi_1, \psi_2]^T$ where both ψ_1 and ψ_2 are chosen as rectangular pulse signals with amplitude 100. In addition, based on Proposition 4, the standby time is $T_{\max} = \bar{\alpha} = 10\text{s}$.

Fig. 10. Discrimination result of the fault discrimination scheme for the replay attack scenario using the method in [25], [26].

The detection and discrimination results are shown in Fig. 9 where the cyan colour represents the standby time. It can be viewed from the two sub-figures of the left-hand side of Fig. 9 that in the integrity attack case, r exceeds \bar{r}_d and \bar{r}_f at about $T_d = 28.3\text{s}$ and 29.1s respectively, and keeps lower than \bar{r}_a until $T_d + T_{\max} = 38.3$. Based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, a threat is detected at $T_d = 28.3\text{s}$, and identified as an attack at $T_d + T_{\max} = 38.3\text{s}$.

In addition, from the right-hand side of Fig. 9, we can observe that in the fault and integrity attack scenario, r exceeds \bar{r}_d at $T_d = 26\text{s}$, and exceeds \bar{r}_a at 35.0s before $T_d + T_{\max}$. Based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, the threat is identified as the composition of the fault and the attack at 35s. The watermark $w(t)$ exhibits identical behavior in both the integrity attack scenario and the fault and integrity attack scenario, with $q(t)$ displaying the same behavior as well. At about 28.3s (see the green diamond mark), $w(t)$ has an outer switch, whereas no outer switch occurs to $q(t)$, which verifies

condition (53) in Proposition 3.

As a comparison, the detection and discrimination result for the integrity attack based on the watermark approach in [25], [26] is shown in Fig. 10. This verifies that the integrity attack scenario, and the fault and integrity attack scenario cannot be identified based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*. The reason is that the watermark generated randomly or stochastically is not sensitive to stealthy integrity attacks.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed a sensor switching watermark methodology, combined with a *bi-layer decision strategy*, for detecting and discriminating among physical faults and MITM cyber attacks. Suitable design conditions have been developed for the switch values and time instants which, by combining random elements and private time seeds, make the watermark unpredictable to the attacker. Moreover, analytical results have been developed that guarantee the detection and discrimination among physical faults and MITM cyber attacks. Furthermore, it was demonstrated how a Lorenz system enables the practical satisfaction of the time seed design conditions. This type of time seeds may achieve similar confidentiality as the noise injection-based privacy protection methodology in [46], which will be verified in our future work.

APPENDIX

Proof of Theorem 1. (a) Without loss of generality, suppose that the outer switches are synchronized at $t_{w,i}$ and $t_{q,i}$ for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$, and an outer switch occurs in \mathcal{W} at $t_{w,k}$. Then, Theorem 1(a) can be proved if \mathcal{Q} also has an outer switch at $t_{w,k}$. Note that in this case, $q(t_{w,k}) = w(t_{w,k})$. In the following, we prove this for the nominal and fault scenarios. It follows from (34a) in Lemma 3 that $y_q(t_{w,k}) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+)$ in TPq (31) can be written as $y_q(t_{w,k}) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+) = y_p(t_{w,k}^+) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+) + w(t_{w,k}^+) - q(t_{w,k})$. Based on w and q in (16), we have $|w(t_{w,k}^+) - q(t_{w,k})| = |w(t_{w,k}^+) - w(t_{w,k})| = |\theta_1 + \theta_2|$. By using the reverse triangle inequality of vector norms, $|y_q(t_{w,k}) - y_p(t_{q,k-1}^+)| \geq |\theta_1 + \theta_2| - |y_p(t_{w,k}^+) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+)|$. Since in both the nominal and fault cases, $|y_p| \leq \Upsilon$ (see \mathcal{Y} in (10)), we have $|y_p(t_{w,k}^+) - y_p(t_{w,k-1}^+)| \leq 2\Upsilon$. Thus, θ_1, θ_2 and η satisfying (35a) can trigger TPq (31) at $t_{w,k}$, and an outer switch occurs in \mathcal{Q} at $t_{w,k}$ in the nominal and fault cases.

(b) We now prove that (35b) and (35c) guarantee that no outer switch is triggered in \mathcal{Q} at any time belonging to S_w^{tr} and S_w^i . Regarding (35b), for any $\bar{t}_{w,k} \in S_w^{tr}$, it follows from (34a) in Lemma 3 that $y_q(\bar{t}_{w,k}) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)$ in TPq (31) can be written as $y_q(\bar{t}_{w,k}) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+) = y_p(\bar{t}_{w,k}^+) - w(\bar{t}_{w,k}) + w(\bar{t}_{w,k}^+) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)$, where $q(\bar{t}_{w,k}) = w(\bar{t}_{w,k})$ is used. Based on watermark w in (16), we have $|w(\bar{t}_{w,k}^+) - w(\bar{t}_{w,k})| = |\theta_2|$. Furthermore, by using the triangle inequality of vector norms, $|y_q(\bar{t}_{w,k}) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)| \leq |\theta_2| + |y_p(\bar{t}_{w,k}^+) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)|$. Since in the nominal and fault cases, $|y_p(\bar{t}_{w,k}^+) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)| \leq 2\Upsilon$, θ_2 and η satisfying (35b) guarantees (37). Hence, TPq in (31) is not triggered at $\bar{t}_{w,k}$, and the inner switch in \mathcal{W} at $\bar{t}_{w,k}$ does not lead to any outer switch in \mathcal{Q} .

In terms of (35c), for any $t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j \in S_w^i$, it follows from (34a) in Lemma 3 that $y_q(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)$ in TPq

(31) can be written as $y_q(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+) = y_p(t_{w,k}^+ + \Delta t_k^j) + w(t_{w,k}^+ + \Delta t_k^j) - w(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j) - y_p(t_{w,k}^+)$ where $q(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j) = w(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j)$ is used. Based on (16), we have $|w(t_{w,k}^+ + \Delta t_k^j) - w(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j)| = |\theta_1|$. Furthermore, by using the triangle inequality of vector norms, $|y_q(t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j) - y_p(t_{q,k}^+)| \leq |\theta_1| + |y_p(t_{w,k}^+ + \Delta t_k^j) - y_p(t_{w,k}^+)|$. Since in the nominal and fault cases, $|y_p(t_{w,k}^+ + \Delta t_k^j) - y_p(t_{w,k}^+)| \leq 2\Upsilon$, θ_1 and η satisfying (35c) can guarantee (37), indicating that TPq (31) is not triggered at $t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j$. Hence, the inner switch of \mathcal{W} at $t_{w,k} + \Delta t_k^j$ does not lead to an outer switch in \mathcal{Q} . \square

Proof of Theorem 2. (i) Based on Theorem 1, $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_f(t)$ for all $t \geq T_f$ in the fault scenario. Then, based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, the fault can be identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$ if $\|r(T_d)\| > \bar{r}_d(T_d)$. According to Theorem 1, the outer switches in \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are synchronized in the fault scenario, which indicates that $w = q$. Thus, we have $y_q - y_p = 0$. From (30), $r(t)$ in the fault scenario satisfies

$$\|r(t)\| \geq \|M_{S_f}(T_f, t)f(t)\| - \|r_d(t)\|. \quad (67)$$

Based on Lemma 2(i), $\|r_d(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_d(t)$. A sufficient condition to guarantee $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_d(t)$ for some $t > T_f$, is given by

$$\|M_{S_f}(T_f, t)f(t)\| > 2\bar{r}_d(t). \quad (68)$$

Note that it follows from (4) in Lemma 1 that

$$\|M_{S_f}(T_f, t)f(t)\| \geq \frac{\sqrt{\kappa}}{\sqrt{t - T_f}} \|S_f\|_- \|f(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}. \quad (69)$$

Hence, (68) is guaranteed by (40) at $t = T_d$.

(b) Based on Theorem 1, $\|r(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_a(t)$ for all $t \geq T_a$ in the attack scenario. Then, based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, the attack scenario can be identified at $T_d + T_{\max}$, if there exists $T_d > T_a$ such that $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_f(t)$. In the attack case, by using the reverse triangle inequality, r in (30) satisfies

$$\|r(t)\| \geq \|M_{S_a}(T_a, t)a_{eq}(t)\| - \|r_d(t)\|. \quad (70)$$

Based on Lemma 2(i), $\|r_d(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_d(t)$. From Lemma 2(ii), the condition to guarantee $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_f(t)$ for some $t > T_a$ is

$$\|M_{S_a}(T_a, t)a_{eq}(t)\| > 2\bar{r}_d(t) + \bar{r}_{f0}(t). \quad (71)$$

Note that it follows from (4) in Lemma 1 that

$$\|M_{S_a}a_{eq}(t)\| \geq \frac{\sqrt{\kappa}}{\sqrt{t - T_a}} \|S_a\|_- \|a_{eq}(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}. \quad (72)$$

Hence, (71) is guaranteed by (41) at $t = T_d$.

(c) Based on the *bi-layer decision strategy*, the attack and fault scenario is identified at t_a if there exist T_d such that $\|r(T_d)\| \geq \bar{r}_d(T_d)$, and $t_a \in (T_d, T_d + T_{\max}]$ such that $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_a(t)$. In the attack and fault case, by using the reverse triangle inequality, r in (30) satisfies

$$\|r(t)\| \geq \|M_{S_{af}}(T_{af}, t)[f^T(t), a_{eq}^T(t)]^T\| - \|r_d(t)\|. \quad (73)$$

The condition (42a) guarantees $\|r(T_d)\| \geq \bar{r}_d(T_d)$. The proof is similar to that for (a) and is omitted here. In addition, based on Lemma 2(i), $\|r_d(t)\| \leq \bar{r}_d(t)$. Thus, from Lemma 2(iii), the condition to guarantee $\|r(t)\| > \bar{r}_a(t)$ for some $t > T_a$ is

$$\|M_{S_{af}}(T_{af}, t)[f^T(t), a_{eq}^T(t)]^T\| > 2\bar{r}_d(t) + \bar{r}_{a0}(t). \quad (74)$$

Note that it follows from (4) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \|M_{S_{af}}(T_{af}, t)[f^T(t), a_{eq}^T(t)]^T\| \\ & \geq \frac{\sqrt{\kappa}}{\sqrt{t - T_{af}}} \|S_{af}\|_- \| [a_{eq}^T(t), f^T(t)]^T \|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}. \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

Hence, (74) is guaranteed by (42b) at $t = t_a$. \square

Proof for Proposition 1. It is straightforward that the outer switches of \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are asynchronized in the special case that an outer switch is triggered in \mathcal{Q} at T_a . So in the following, we study the general case that no outer switch is triggered in \mathcal{Q} at T_a . The upper bound of α_k guarantees that (43) is well defined, i.e., $\max_{k \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, N]}} \{\alpha_k\}$ exists. Under condition (43), there exists a $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, k-1]}$ that the recording procedure of the replay attack is initiated at $T_a - T_r \in (t_{w, k-k_0-1}, t_{w, k-k_0}]$. Since during the time interval $(t_{w, k-k_0+i-1}, t_{w, k-k_0+i}]$ for any $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$, the outer switches between \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are synchronized, then $w(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) = q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+)$. In addition, note that $a_y(t_{q, k-1}^+) = 0$ and for any $t \in [T_a, T_a + T_r]$, it follows from (20) that

$$a_y(t) + y_p(t) = y_p(t - T_r) + w(t - T_r) - w(t). \quad (76)$$

Then, we test the triggering condition of the remover \mathcal{Q} at $t_{q, k-k_0+i} + T_r$ for any $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$ based on the equivalent triggering condition (34a) in Lemma 3. From (76), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) \\ & + q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) = y_p(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) + w(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) \\ & - q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - y_p(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) - w(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) \\ & - a_y(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) + q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+). \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

(i) For $i = 0$, since $a_y(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) = 0$, we then have

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) \\ & + q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) = y_p(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) - y_p(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) \\ & + q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) - q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r), \end{aligned} \quad (78)$$

where $-w(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) + q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) = 0$ and $w(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) = q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+)$ are used. An outer switch occurs in \mathcal{Q} at $t_{q, k-k_0} + T_r$ if (44) holds for $i = 0$.

(ii) For the case $i \geq 1$, it follows from (76) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) \\ & + q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+) = y_p(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) + q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+) \\ & - q(t_{q, k-k_0+i}^+ + T_r) - y_p(t_{q, k+i-1}^+ - T_r) \\ & - q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+ - T_r) + q(t_{q, k+i-1}^+). \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

Hence, from condition (44), we can induce that the triggering condition of \mathcal{Q} at $t_{q, k-k_0+i} + T_r$ is satisfied and thus, an outer switch of \mathcal{Q} occurs. Hence, the result follows. \square

Proof for Proposition 2. Based on the result in Proposition 1, in the presence of the replay attack at T_a , for some $i \in \mathbb{N}_{[0, k_0-1]}$, q satisfies

$$q(t) = \begin{cases} q_{k-k_0+i}(t), & \forall t \in (t_{q, k-k_0+i}, t_{q, k-k_0+i+1}], \\ q_{k+i}(t), & \forall t \in (t_{q, k+i}, t_{q, k+i+1}]. \end{cases}$$

From (20) and $w(t - T_r) = q(t - T_r)$ for $t - T_r \leq T_a$, it follows that the equivalent attack signal a_{eq} in (19) satisfies $a_{eq}(t) = y_p(t - T_r) - y_p(t) + q(t - T_r) - q(t)$. Hence, from (10), we have

$$\|a_{eq}\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} \geq \|q(t - T_r) - q(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} - 2\kappa\Upsilon. \quad (80)$$

Based on Design Condition 1(i), for any $t \in (t_{k-k_0+i}^q, t_{k+i}^q]$ such that the deviation between functions q_{k-k_0+i} and q_{k+i} defined in (38) satisfies $\|q_{k-k_0+i}(t - T_r) - q_{k+i}(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} = \|\Delta q_{k-k_0+i, k+i}(t, T_r)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} \geq \Delta \bar{q}(t)$. Hence, based on Theorem 2(iii) and the design condition (39), the replay attack and fault scenario can be detected at T_d and discriminated at t_a if the inequality (51) is satisfied.

Recalling the definition of t_k^q above (38), we have $t_{k-k_0+i}^q > t_{q, k+i}$ and $t_{k+i}^q \leq t_{q, k+i+1}$. Hence, (50) follows. Furthermore, based on Proposition 1, we have $T_{\max} = t_{q, k+i+1} - t_{q, k-1}$. Note that the upper bound $\bar{\alpha}$ of α_k given in (32b) guarantees that $t_{q, k+i+1} - t_{q, k-1} \leq (i+2)\bar{\alpha}$. Hence, $T_{\max} = (i+2)\bar{\alpha}$. Moreover, based on Theorem 2(ii) and the design condition (39), the replay attack can be detected and discriminated if the inequality (52) is satisfied. \square

Proof for Proposition 3. Without loss of generality, we suppose that the attack occurs at T_a , and the outer switches in \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} are synchronized at $t_{w, 0}, \dots, t_{w, k-1}$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, N]}$. At time $\tau_a \in (t_{w, k-1}, t_{w, k-1} + \alpha_k]$, the condition (53a) triggers an outer switch in \mathcal{W} . We then test the triggering condition (34a) in Lemma 3 for the remover \mathcal{Q} as follows: $\tilde{y}_w(\tau_a^+) - \tilde{y}_w(t_{q, k-1}^+) - q(\tau_a) + q(t_{q, k-1}^+) = y_{pn}(\tau_a^+) + w(\tau_a^+) - w(\tau_a) - y_{pn}(t_{q, k-1}^+)$, where $y_p(t) + a_y(t) = y_{pn}(t)$, $q(\tau_a) = w(\tau_a)$ and $-w(t_{q, k-1}^+) + q(t_{q, k-1}^+) = 0$ are used. Note that it follows from (53b) and (17) that $\theta_{2w}(\tau_a) = 0$ and then, $w(\tau_a^+) - w(\tau_a) = 2\theta_1$. Hence, the switch triggering condition (34a) is not triggered at τ_a and thus, no outer switch of \mathcal{Q} occurs at τ_a . Hence, the outer switch asynchronization between \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{Q} occurs at τ_a . \square

Proof for Proposition 4. As in Proposition 4, in the presence of the integrity attack, an outer switch occurs in \mathcal{W} at $\tau_a \in (t_{w, k-1}, t_{w, k-1} + \alpha_k]$, but no outer switch occurs in \mathcal{Q} at τ_a . We can then induce that $w(t) = w_k(t)$ and $q(t) = w_{k-1}(t)$, and from (23), it follows that $a_{eq} = w(t) - q(t) = w_k(t) - q_{k-1}(t)$. Based on Design Condition 1(i), there exists $t \in (t_k^w, t_{k-1}^w]$, $\|w_k(t) - w_{k-1}(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} = \|\Delta w_{k, k-1}(t, 0)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa} \geq \Delta \bar{w}(t)$. Hence, (55) suffices to guarantee (42). The maximal time required to identify the attack scenario is obtained by noting that $t_a \in (t_k^w, t_{k-1}^w]$ in (54). Recalling the definition of t_k^w above (38), we have $t_k^w > t_{w, k-1}$ and $t_{k-1}^w \leq t_{w, k}$. Hence, $T_{\max} = t_{w, k} - t_{w, k-1} \leq \bar{\alpha}$. Moreover, based on the design condition (39), (56) guarantees (41) in Theorem 2. \square

Proof of Theorem 3. Based on the property of the map g given in Lemma 4, the condition (64) indicates that $\xi_{k_1}^0$ is not on the orbit $\{\xi_{k_2}^j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ starting from $\xi_{k_2}^0$. Thus, we can obtain

$$\xi_{k_1}^{j+m} \neq \xi_{k_2}^j, \quad \forall j, m \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (81)$$

Without loss of generality, we suppose that $t_{k_1} = t_{h, k_1} - \varepsilon + \Delta t_{k_1}^{m+1} = t_{h, k_2} + \Delta t_{k_2}^1$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$ and some ε such

that $t_{h,k_1} - \varepsilon = t_{h,k_2}$. Then, $\Delta t_{k_1}^{m+1} = \Delta t_{k_2}^1$. Based on (61), we have

$$\xi_{k_1}^1 + \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} (\xi_{k_1}^j + 20) = \xi_{k_2}^1. \quad (82)$$

Then, the proof is conducted using a contradiction approach. Suppose that $\Delta h_{k_1,k_2}(t, \varepsilon) = 0$ for any $t \in [t_{k_1}^h, t_{k_2}^h]$. Then, based on (61), for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n \geq m+2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{k_1}^1 + \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} (\xi_{k_1}^j + 20) + \sum_{j=m+2}^n (\xi_{k_1}^j + 20) \\ = \xi_{k_2}^1 + \sum_{j=2}^{n-m} (\xi_{k_2}^j + 20). \end{aligned} \quad (83)$$

From the above two equalities (82) and (83), we can induce $\sum_{j=m+2}^n (\xi_{k_1}^j + 20) = \sum_{j=2}^{n-m} (\xi_{k_2}^j + 20)$, $\forall n \geq m+2$. Furthermore, it is induced when $n = m+2$, $\xi_{k_1}^{m+2} = \xi_{k_2}^2$, and then $\xi_{k_1}^{j+m} = \xi_{k_2}^j$, $\forall j \geq 2$, which contradicts (81). Hence, there exists some j and time $t \in (\Delta t_k^j, \Delta t_k^{j+1}] \subseteq (t_{k_1}^h, t_{k_2}^h]$ such that

$$\Delta h_{k_1,k_2}(t, \varepsilon) = h_{k_1}(t - \varepsilon) - h_{k_2}(t) \neq 0. \quad (84)$$

Furthermore, with the condition (65), we can induce that there exists a time t such that

$$h_{k_1}(t - \varepsilon)h_{k_2}(t) = \begin{cases} \theta_1^2, & \forall t \in [t - \kappa, t - \frac{1}{2}\kappa), \\ -\theta_1^2, & \forall t \in [t - \frac{1}{2}\kappa, t), \end{cases}$$

which indicates $\frac{1}{\kappa} \int_{t-\kappa}^t h_{k_1}(\tau - \varepsilon)h_{k_2}(\tau) d\tau = 0$, and thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Delta h_{k_1,k_2}(t, \varepsilon)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}^2 &= \|h_{k_1}(t - \varepsilon)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}^2 + \|h_{k_2}(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}, \kappa}^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\kappa} \int_{t-\kappa}^t h_{k_1}(\tau)h_{k_2}(\tau - \varepsilon) d\tau = 2\theta_1^2. \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

Hence, the inequality (39) of Design Condition 1(i) can be guaranteed by (66). \square

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Zhang, A. Kasis, M. M. Polycarpou, and T. Parisini, "A sensor watermarking design for threat discrimination," in *11th IFAC Sympo. Fault Detection, Supervision and Saf. Tech. Processes SAFEPROCESS*, vol. 55, no. 6, 2022, pp. 433–438.
- [2] D. G. Eliades, S. G. Vrachimis, A. Moghaddam, I. Tzortzis, and M. M. Polycarpou, "Contamination event diagnosis in drinking water networks: A review," *Annu. Rev. Control*, vol. 55, pp. 420–441, 2023.
- [3] H. Sandberg, A. Teixeira, and K. H. Johansson, "On security indices for state estimators in power networks," in *1st workshop secure control systems, Stockholm, 2010*, 2010.
- [4] A. Cardenas, S. Amin, and S. Sastry, "Secure control: Towards survivable cyber-physical systems," in *28th Int. C. Distrib. Comput. Syst. Workshops*, 2008, pp. 495–500.
- [5] R. Thomas, "Triton malware spearheads latest attacks on industrial systems," www.mcafee.com/blogs/other-blogs/mcafee-labs/triton-malware-spearheads-latest-generation-of-attacks-on-industrial-systems/, 2018.
- [6] K. Zhang, C. Keliris, T. Parisini, and M. M. Polycarpou, "Identification of sensor replay attacks and physical faults for cyber-physical systems," *IEEE Control Syst. Lett.*, vol. 6, pp. 1178–1183, 2021.
- [7] K. Zhang, C. Keliris, M. M. Polycarpou, and T. Parisini, "Discrimination between replay attacks and sensor faults for cyber-physical systems via event-triggered communication," *Eur. J. Control*, vol. 62, pp. 47–56, 2021.
- [8] X. Zhang, M. M. Polycarpou, and T. Parisini, "Fault diagnosis of a class of nonlinear uncertain systems with lipschitz nonlinearities using adaptive estimation," *Automatica*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 290–299, 2010.
- [9] K. Zhang, C. Keliris, M. M. Polycarpou, and T. Parisini, "Detecting stealthy integrity attacks in a class of nonlinear cyber-physical systems: A backward-in-time approach," *Automatica*, vol. 141, p. 110262, 2022.
- [10] R. M. Ferrari and A. M. Teixeira, "Detection and isolation of replay attacks through sensor watermarking," in *20th IFAC World Congr.*, vol. 50, no. 1. Elsevier, 2017, pp. 7363–7368.
- [11] Y. Mo and B. Sinopoli, "Secure control against replay attacks," in *47th Annu Allerton Conf. Commun. Control Comput.*, 2009, pp. 911–918.
- [12] R. S. Smith, "Covert misappropriation of networked control systems: Presenting a feedback structure," *IEEE Control Syst. Mag.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 82–92, 2015.
- [13] A. Barboni, H. Rezaee, F. Boem, and T. Parisini, "Detection of covert cyber-attacks in interconnected systems: A distributed model-based approach," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 3728–3741, 2020.
- [14] F. Pasqualetti, F. Dörfler, and F. Bullo, "Attack detection and identification in cyber-physical systems," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 2715–2729, 2013.
- [15] K. Zhang, C. Keliris, T. Parisini, and M. M. Polycarpou, "Stealthy integrity attacks for a class of nonlinear cyber-physical systems," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 67, pp. 6723–6730, 2022.
- [16] S. Chockalingam, W. Pieters, A. Teixeira, and P. van Gelder, "Probability elicitation for bayesian networks to distinguish between intentional attacks and accidental technical failures," *J. Inf. Secur. Appl.*, vol. 75, pp. 1–17, 2023.
- [17] Y. Mo, S. Weerakkody, and B. Sinopoli, "Physical authentication of control systems: Designing watermarked control inputs to detect counterfeit sensor outputs," *IEEE Control Syst. Mag.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 93–109, 2015.
- [18] A. Gallo, S. Anand, A. M. Teixeira, and R. M. Ferrari, "Design of multiplicative watermarking against covert attacks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.00555*, 2021.
- [19] M. Porter, P. Hespanhol, A. Aswani, M. Johnson-Roberson, and R. Vasudevan, "Detecting generalized replay attacks via time-varying dynamic watermarking," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 66, no. 8, pp. 3502–3517, 2021.
- [20] F. Farokhi, I. Shames, and N. Batterham, "Secure and private control using semi-homomorphic encryption," *Control Eng. Pract.*, vol. 67, pp. 13–20, 2017.
- [21] M. S. Darup, A. Redder, I. Shames, F. Farokhi, and D. Quevedo, "Towards encrypted mpc for linear constrained systems," *IEEE Control Syst. Lett.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 195–200, 2018.
- [22] F. G. Märmol, C. Sorge, O. Ugus, and G. M. Pérez, "Do not snoop my habits: preserving privacy in the smart grid," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 50, no. 5, pp. 166–172, 2012.
- [23] R. M. Ferrari and A. M. Teixeira, "A switching multiplicative watermarking scheme for detection of stealthy cyber-attacks," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 2558–2573, 2020.
- [24] D. Ye, T. Zhang, and G. Guo, "Stochastic coding detection scheme in cyber-physical systems against replay attack," *Inf. Sci.*, vol. 481, pp. 432–444, 2019.
- [25] J. Huang, D. W. Ho, F. Li, W. Yang, and Y. Tang, "Secure remote state estimation against linear man-in-the-middle attacks using watermarking," *Automatica*, vol. 121, p. 109182, 2020.
- [26] T. Li, Z. Wang, L. Zou, B. Chen, and L. Yu, "A dynamic encryption-decryption scheme for replay attack detection in cyber-physical systems," *Automatica*, vol. 151, p. 110926, 2023.
- [27] M. Green and D. J. Limebeer, *Linear robust control*. Courier Corporation, 2012.
- [28] J. Liu, J. L. Wang, and G. Yang, "An LMI approach to minimum sensitivity analysis with application to fault detection," *Automatica*, vol. 41, no. 11, pp. 1995–2004, 2005.
- [29] X. Li and H. H. Liu, "Characterization of H_- index for linear time-varying systems," *Automatica*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 1449–1457, 2013.
- [30] H. Khalil, *Nonlinear systems*. Prentice Hall, 2002.
- [31] S. Raghavan and J. K. Hedrick, "Observer design for a class of nonlinear systems," *Int. J. Control*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 515–528, 1994.
- [32] S. Ding, *Model-based fault diagnosis techniques: design schemes, algorithms, and tools*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2008.
- [33] R. Rajamani and A. Ganguli, "Sensor fault diagnostics for a class of nonlinear systems using linear matrix inequalities," *Int. J. Control*, vol. 77, no. 10, pp. 920–930, 2004.
- [34] R. Rajamani, "Observers for lipschitz nonlinear systems," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 397–401, 1998.
- [35] W. Chen, J. Yang, L. Guo, and S. Li, "Disturbance-observer-based control and related methods—an overview," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 1083–1095, 2015.

- [36] R. S. Smith, "A decoupled feedback structure for covertly appropriating networked control systems," in *18th IFAC World Congr.*, vol. 44, no. 1. Elsevier, 2011, pp. 90–95.
- [37] A. M. Teixeira, I. Shames, H. Sandberg, and K. H. Johansson, "A secure control framework for resource-limited adversaries," *Automatica*, vol. 51, pp. 135–148, 2015.
- [38] K. Zhang, M. M. Polycarpou, and T. Parisini, "Enhanced anomaly detector for nonlinear cyber-physical systems against stealthy integrity attacks," in *21st IFAC World Congr.*, vol. 53, no. 2. Elsevier, 2020, pp. 13 682–13 687.
- [39] J. Milošević, A. M. Teixeira, K. H. Johansson, and H. Sandberg, "Actuator security indices based on perfect undetectability: Computation, robustness, and sensor placement," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 3816–3831, 2020.
- [40] Y. Mo, R. Chabukwar, and B. Sinopoli, "Detecting integrity attacks on SCADA systems," *IEEE Trans Control Syst. Technol.*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 1396–1407, 2013.
- [41] A. Sargolzaei, K. Yen, and M. N. Abdelghani, "Delayed inputs attack on load frequency control in smart grid," in *ISGT 2014*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 1–5.
- [42] M. Viana, "What's new on lorenz strange attractors?" *The Mathematical Intelligencer*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 6–19, 2000.
- [43] C. Murguia, I. Shames, F. Farokhi, and D. Nešić, "Information-theoretic privacy through chaos synchronization and optimal additive noise," in *Privacy in Dynamical Systems*. Springer, 2020, pp. 103–129.
- [44] C. Knapp and G. Carter, "The generalized correlation method for estimation of time delay," *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 320–327, 1976.
- [45] M. Hirsch, S. Smale, and R. L. Devaney, *Differential equations, dynamical systems, and an introduction to chaos*. Academic press, 2012.
- [46] J. Wang, J. Zhang, and X. He, "Differentially private distributed algorithms for stochastic aggregative games," *Automatica*, vol. 142, p. 110440, 2022.

Thomas Parisini (Fellow, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in electronic engineering and computer science from the University of Genoa, Italy, in 1993. He was an Associate Professor with Politecnico di Milano, Italy. He currently holds the Chair of industrial control and is the Head of the Control and Power Research Group, Imperial College London, U.K. He also holds a Distinguished Professorship at Aalborg University, Denmark. Since 2001, he has been the Danieli Endowed Chair of automation engineering with the University of Trieste, Italy, where from 2009 to 2012, he was the Deputy Rector. In 2023, he held a "Scholar-in-Residence" visiting position with Digital Futures-KTH, Sweden. He has coauthored a research monograph in the Communication and Control Series (Springer Nature) and over 400 publications, including journal articles, book chapters, and conference papers. In 2023 he was the recipient of the Knighthood of the Order of Merit of the Italian Republic for scientific achievements abroad awarded by the Italian President of the Republic. In 2018 he received the Honorary Doctorate from the University of Aalborg, Denmark and in 2024, the IEEE CSS Transition to Practice Award. Moreover, he was awarded the 2007 IEEE Distinguished Member Award, and was co-recipient of the IFAC Best Application Paper Prize of the Journal of Process Control for the period 2011-2013 and of the 2004 Outstanding Paper Award of IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks. In 2016, he was awarded as Principal Investigator with Imperial of the H2020 European Union flagship Teaming Project KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence led by the University of Cyprus with an overall budget of over 40 million Euros. He was the 2021-2022 President of the IEEE Control Systems Society and the Editor-in-Chief of IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology (2009-2016). He is currently an Editor of *Automatica* and the Editor-in-Chief of the *European Journal of Control*. He is a Fellow of IFAC, a Member of IEEE TAB Periodicals Review and Advisory Committee and chairs the IEEE CSS Awards Committee.

Kangkang Zhang is a Professor of the College of Automation Engineering at the Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics (NUAA). He received his Ph.D degree from NUAA in 2018. During the period 2017-2018, he was a visiting Ph.D student at University of Kent. From 2019 to 2022, he was a Research Associate at the KIOS Research and Innovation Center, University of Cyprus. He worked as a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellow in the Control & Power Group at Imperial College London.

His research interests include analysis, diagnosis, and control of complex and cyber-physical systems in the presence of cyber-physical threats. His thesis received the CAA Excellent Doctoral Dissertation Award from the Chinese Association of Automation.

Andreas Kasis is a Research Lecturer with the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus. He received the B.A. degree (first class) in electrical and information sciences and the M.Eng. degree (distinction) in information and computer engineering from Robinson College, University of Cambridge, in 2013 and his Ph.D. degree from University of Cambridge in 2017. He was a Research Associate with the Control group at the University of Cambridge until 2019. He was awarded a Marie

Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) individual fellowship for research on power systems. His research interests focus on the analysis, control, optimization, and security of complex, cyber-physical, and networked systems with applications on smart power grids.

Marios M. Polycarpou (F'06) is a Professor of Electrical and Computer Engineering and the Director of the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence at the University of Cyprus. He is also a Founding Member of the Cyprus Academy of Sciences, Letters, and Arts, an Honorary Professor of Imperial College London, and a Member of Academia Europaea (The Academy of Europe). He received the B.A degree in Computer Science and the B.Sc. in Electrical Engineering, both from Rice University, USA in 1987, and the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in Electrical Engineering from the University of Southern California, in 1989 and 1992 respectively. His teaching and research interests are in intelligent systems and networks, adaptive and learning control systems, fault diagnosis, machine learning, and critical infrastructure systems.

Prof. Polycarpou is the recipient of the 2023 IEEE Frank Rosenblatt Technical Field Award and the 2016 IEEE Neural Networks Pioneer Award. He is a Fellow of IEEE and IFAC. He served as the President of the IEEE Computational Intelligence Society (2012-2013), as the President of the European Control Association (2017-2019), and as the Editor-in-Chief of the IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems (2004-2010). Prof. Polycarpou currently serves on the Editorial Boards of the Proceedings of the IEEE and the Annual Reviews in Control. His research work has been funded by several agencies and industry in Europe and the United States, including the prestigious European Research Council (ERC) Advanced Grant, the ERC Synergy Grant and the EU-Widening Teaming program.